

Quantitative Scenarios for Low Carbon Futures of the European Energy System on Country, Region and Local Level

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List of Acronyms

BECCS	Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage
CAES	Compressed Air Energy Storage
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
CO ₂	Carbon-Dioxide
DT	Directed Transition
GD	Gradual Development
GW	Gigawatt
LAU	Local Administrative Unit
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
PHS	Pumped Hydro Storage
PJ	Petajoule
PV	Photo-Voltaic
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SC	Societal Commitment
TF	Techno-Friendly
TWh	Terawatt-hours

1 Introduction

1.1 Scenario results at different spatial granularity levels

Within the Open ENTRANCE project, great emphasis is placed on achieving consistent and coherent methodologies and quantitative scenario results at different levels of spatial granularity when generating decarbonization scenarios of the European energy system. Starting with the pan-European system boundary, for which the corresponding "draft" scenario results based on the 4 Open ENTRANCE storylines have already been presented in Deliverable D3.1 [1], consistent with the European compatible CO₂ content for the 1.5/2.0°C maximum global temperature increase targets, the spatial system boundaries of the presentation of the scenario results are increasingly narrowed in this report. Breaking down aggregate modeling results to ever smaller spatial system boundaries is very important in practice for energy policy decision making. This also eliminates the regularly voiced criticism that modeling results are too aggregated and thus useless for practical decision-making.

Not least for this reason, Deliverable D3.2 attempts to present methods and algorithms based on country results and to break them down over the various NUTS levels (Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics) to the smallest administrative unit (Local Administrative Unit, LAU) level and even beyond. Thus, with a kind of "last mile" analysis, a contribution is made here to make energy policy decision-making very tangible in very small administrative units such as municipalities, neighbourhoods, buildings and ultimately at the individual end user.

In order to be able to achieve robust scenario results, in addition to the necessary consistency of the empirical input data such as (primary) energy prices in the scenario analysis across the various spatial aggregation levels, particular attention must also be paid to the corresponding CO₂ price, which defines the economic viability limits of the various technology portfolios. The importance of the role of the CO₂ price is often forgotten or not properly depicted, especially in the analysis of the decarbonization of regional or local energy systems. This then decisively distorts the favoured energy technologies or technology portfolios in the substitution of fossil fuels. Therefore, in the presentation of results and the discussion or synthesis of the results in this report, Deliverable D3.2, the role and importance of CO₂ prices, which form an essential cornerstone of the Open ENTRANCE scenario framework, is repeatedly emphasised.

Against the background of the above introduction, the aim of the materials presented in this report, Deliverable D3.2, is defined in more detail below.

1.2 Objectives and scope of this report

The core objectives and scope of this report can be divided into two clusters and summarized as follows:

- First, taking into account the lessons learned from the "draft" scenario results at the pan-European level [1], which were obtained during the verification and applications to the case studies. Based on that, selective improvements of the corresponding input data basis as well as refinements of the GENeSYS-MOD model with respect to different functionalities and the temporal resolution of the simulations have been made. Afterwards, the final Open ENTRANCE scenario model runs on a pan-European level as well as on the level of the individual European countries have been executed.
- Second, the development of consistent and coherent methods and algorithms to break down country-specific GENeSYS-MOD modeling results across the different NUTS levels to the smallest administrative unit level such as municipalities, city districts, neighborhoods, buildings, and finally to the individual end user. To our knowledge, there has not yet been this ambition to perform concrete energy system analyses to achieve specific climate goals across all levels of aggregation in a consistent and very concrete way down to individual end users. These types of "last mile" to end-user analyses, presented here in Deliverable D3.2, are increasingly important to get an idea of how to respond in practice in a very concrete way to the climate challenges ahead.

For local-level energy system analyses, which are more small-scale than the regional analyses done directly with the GENeSYS-MOD model, among others, the following consistent empirical data settings are of particular importance:

- Input data settings of the modelling or analysis such as primary energy prices, technology and network costs, etc.
- Aggregated empirical modelling results in the respective sector of analysis as well as the corresponding endogenous results such as CO₂ price trajectories, which describe the decarbonization path in the individual scenarios and also form the cornerstones and determine the economic trade-offs for local analyses of the energy system.

Finally, Figure 1–1, already presented in Deliverable D3.1, places the work presented in this Deliverable D3.2 (red area) in a larger context of the Open ENTRANCE project. Based on various insights gained so far in the Open ENTRANCE project, final pan-European and country-specific results are presented, as well as further more finely granulated results at the lower energy system level.

Figure 1–1 Flowchart of the quantitative scenario generation process in Open ENTRANCE

1.3 Outline of this report

This Deliverable D3.2 presents in addition to updated pan-European scenario results (see also [1]) selected highlights of European country-specific and region-specific scenario results as well as consistent and coherent results on local community, neighborhood and individual building level. Deliverable D3.2 is organized as follows:

- Chapter 2 presents the refinements to the GENeSYS-MOD model compared to the version used to generate the scenario results in Deliverable D3.1. These refinements include slight updates to some input data. Selected results from the updated version of the pan-European scenario results are then presented. Finally, we briefly outline how the final scenario results data will be further used (e.g., case study analyses) and processed (e.g., upload to the Open ENTRANCE Scenario Explorer).
- Chapter 3 is devoted to the presentation of European country-specific scenario results. After a European overview of the main scenario outcome indicators, selected countries are presented in more detail. These include Germany, France and Spain. This is followed by a general discussion of the findings from the country-specific results analysis.
- Chapter 4 performs further downscaling of the country-specific scenario results on a representative regional and local level. This is done on the one hand by applying GENeSYS-MOD on a region-specific granularity in two countries (Norway and Turkey) and on the other hand by developing further tailored downscaling techniques on a local community level in Austria. The local-level analyses comprise contributions to municipality, neighborhood and individual building level.
- A synthesis of results is provided in Chapter 5, followed by concluding remarks.
- References and an Appendix conclude this report.

2 Refinements of GENeSYS-MOD and updated pan-European scenario results

This chapter of the report presents the model changes and refinements made to the Global Energy System Model (GENeSYS-MOD) regarding both model and data, and showcases the main results gained from the modeling exercises. More information on model refinements, as well as more detailed results can be found in the Appendix.

2.1 Refinements compared to the version used in Deliverable 3.1

Since the model version used in the Deliverable D3.1 from 2020 (v2.9-oE), several changes have been made to both the model formulation, as well as the data that is being used for the computation of the Open ENTRANCE storylines. These changes include:

- the addition of constraints to better simulate power sector requirements, focusing on required peak capacities and min-run constraints
- the creation of an optional ex-post dispatch model that tests the power sector outputs from GENeSYS-MOD for their feasibility on an hourly basis
- several changes to the model formulation, leading to significant savings in required computational resources and runtimes
- a switch from 2015 to 2018 as a base year for the scenario quantifications
- a major overhaul of the used data assumptions for available technologies

The model source code for GENeSYS-MOD can be found at its public GitLab page under <https://git.tu-berlin.de/genesysmod/genesys-mod-public>. All model files, including data, will be uploaded to this repository, allowing for fully reproducible and therefore transparent model results.

2.1.1 Model improvements

GENeSYS-MOD has been continuously improved over the course of the Open ENTRANCE project. Figure 2-1 outlines the changes and improvements that have been made over the revisions of the model source code.

2.1.1.2 Ex-post dispatch model

To test the effectiveness of the new peaking constraints and other model improvements regarding the feasibility of the resulting electricity system from GENeSYS-MOD, an ex-post dispatch model was added to validate the results (compare [4]). It performs an hourly dispatch analysis of a given year, taking the installed capacities for generation, storages, and transmission lines into account, minimizing the operational costs of the system for that given year. If demand is unable to be met, a costly infeasibility technology can be used by the model, signalling issues with the stability of the resulting electric system – usually caused by an underestimation of required capacities and storages.

Performing this ex-post dispatch analysis shows that the percentage of unmet demand within the Open ENTRANCE scenarios is around 0.5% of total energy demand (see Figure 2–2). This demonstrates that the resulting power system from GENeSYS-MOD is quite close to being fully feasible at an hourly level – albeit only encompassing 72 timesteps per year, instead of 8760. The maximum peak power from this infeasibility lies at 70 GW for all of Europe, in one of the first hours of the year. Figure 2–2 also shows some examples of these dispatch results, displaying the hourly dispatch generated from the Techno-Friendly scenario in the year 2050, for two weeks of both February and July.

Figure 2–2 Graph of resulting hourly dispatch for the European power system (Techno-Friendly, Year 2050) generated by GENeSYS-MOD

2.1.1.3 Performance improvements

In addition to previous performance improvements that focused on the selection of constraints needed to be created at all (therefore limiting the number of choices that the model needs to make to the set of choices that are actually in the realm of possibility)¹, as presented in [5], for version 3.1, quite a few redundancies in computation have been removed as well. In the previous versions, following the Open-Source Energy Modeling System (OSeMOSYS), quite a few redundant calculations took place, making the model somewhat easier to read and understand as a human, but at the same time creating significant amounts of bloat for the computation process. By removing the redundant, intermediary calculations, the runtime memory could be reduced by as much as 42%, while the model runtime was also positively affected, netting a roughly 20% solution time improvement (see Table 2-1).

Table 2-1 Performance statistics of new and old version of GENeSYS-MOD

	v3.1-oE (2022)	v2.9-oE (2020)	Change
runtime memory	1923 MB	3308 MB	-42%
model setup memory	1097 MB	3886 MB	-72%
heap size after solve	1113 MB	3885 MB	-71%
heap size before solve	576 MB	3164 MB	-82%
CPLEX solution time	202s	253s	-20%

This means that given the same computational resources, one could either see a noteworthy change in total runtime of GENeSYS-MOD or could increase the complexity of the researched problem (e.g., by including more time steps, more technological detail, or more regions). This has been taken advantage of for the scenario results in this Deliverable D3.2, where the total level of time resolution is now four times more detailed than in the Deliverable D3.1 from 2020 (at 72 vs. 18 intra-yearly time steps). This comes in addition to the model improvements mentioned in the previous subsections.

¹ An example of this would be the investment decision on a technology that cannot be used in a country, such as offshore wind in Austria, or generation/dispatch decisions for technologies where there is a politically enforced phase-out date (e.g. nuclear in Germany). By removing these non-sensical decisions from the realm of choices, the overall model matrix was significantly reduced.

2.1.2 Input data

While subsection 2.1.1 focused on the improvements and additions from a modelling perspective, representing changes in equations and source code, the underlying data used for quantitative analysis is just as – if not even more – important. Therefore, we have gathered extensive feedback on the input data assumptions, researched new and updated sources, and generally cross-checked the entire GENeSYS-MOD data set for potential shortcomings. Among the main changes for this Deliverable D3.2 are the change of the base year of the model to 2018, the removal of the year 2020 from the model calculations (both due to the close proximity to 2018, as well as being an outlier due to the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic), the update of the price forecasts for fossil fuels, and the change in carbon price assumptions for the scenario calculations.

2.1.2.1 Update of model base year to 2018

Originally, GENeSYS-MOD used 2015 as a base year for its calculations. However, since there has now been significant time since 2015, as well as more and more detailed data being made available on more recent years, a move away from that paradigm was necessary. Instead, 2018 was chosen as a base year for the new computations in Open ENTRANCE, since it was the most recent year where all the necessary sectoral data was available for it at the time of the data preparations. 2020, on the other hand, was removed from the model scope (originally being the first endogenously optimized period of the model horizon). This decision was made since 2020 is both very close to the new base year, as well as generally a strong outlier in terms of energy consumption and emissions, due to the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic. Instead, it was added as an exogenous data point to still be present in the result visualization, e.g., in the scenario explorer of the open platform (for more information on the open platform and further processing of GENeSYS-MOD results, see Section 2.3).

2.1.2.2 Fossil fuel price forecasts

The assumptions on the development of fossil fuel prices shape the cost-competitiveness of renewable energy sources compared to their fossil counterparts, but also generally determine the cost-structure within the model results and are therefore an extremely relevant datapoint for energy system computations. For the previous Pan-European dataset, a uniform development of fossil fuel prices across the different fuels had been assumed. This has now been revised, using the current fossil fuel market outlook data from the World Bank [6]. The source provides fuel market estimates until 2035, which have been used as a starting point for the new Open ENTRANCE dataset. For years after 2030, assumptions on the development have been made according to the storylines described in Deliverable D7.1 [7]. Figure 2–3 shows the development of fossil fuel import prices used in the GENeSYS-MOD scenario calculations (note that Societal Commitment and Techno-Friendly share the same assumed import price on fossil fuels and thus overlap).

Figure 2–3 Updated fossil fuel market assumptions used for the Open ENTRANCE scenarios

2.1.2.3 Carbon price developments

With a change in base year, fossil fuel price forecasts, and other regional and technology data, the endogenous cost structure of GENeSYS-MOD changed as well. Therefore, the CO₂ price developments that have been set for Deliverable D3.1 had to be revised and updated in order to once again match the change in data and assumptions with the scenario targets. As a quick recap, the targets set for each storyline are as follows:

- Directed Transition, Techno-Friendly, and Societal Commitment all aim for a limitation of global warming to 1.5° C. Therefore, the energy system should be emission-free until 2040.
- Directed Transition politically enforces zero emissions (except from technologies with CCS) in 2040, whereas the other two scenarios rely solely on carbon pricing to reach zero emissions in 2040. Also, Directed Transition and Techno-Friendly allow for the use of CCS technologies.
- Gradual Development is set for a 2° C compatible scenario, reaching zero emissions one decade later, in 2050.

Figure 2-4 Updated assumptions on carbon prices used for the Open ENTRANCE scenarios

The carbon prices required to achieve these targets are shown in Figure 2-4. Also, a comparison between the old prices from D3.1 to the new prices used for this report is drawn. One major difference is that the three 1.5° C scenarios are now calibrated towards 2040, while Gradual Development remains calibrated for 2050 (in D3.1, all scenarios were calibrated for 2050). This leads to slightly higher emission costs in 2040 for both Techno-Friendly and Societal Commitment, but a reduction in 2050, while Gradual Development sees a decrease in necessary CO₂ price across the entire model horizon. Directed Transition remains unchanged, even with the new calibration.

2.1.2.4 Other changes in data and assumptions

In addition to the aforementioned changes in core assumptions used for the computation of the model results, many more updates of the Open ENTRANCE dataset have been performed, ranging from technology data to cost estimates for transmission line expansion. The following (non-comprehensive) list highlights the relevant changes in data:

- Inclusion of axis tracking PV as a new renewable generation source
- Addition of several district heating options to the model: district heating is now explicitly modeled and represented in the technology choices (see Supplementary Materials)
- Overhaul of renewable generation timeseries, especially for on- and offshore wind
- Change in costs for transmission capacity expansion
- Revised the pre-installed capacity of technologies for each region
- Added some country-specific political targets (e.g., fossil fuel phase out dates) that were announced since the last iteration of model results
- Several optimizations in the dataset: corrections of faulty entries, naming issues, data transfer problems, etc.

A comprehensive list of used data sources and assumptions can be found in the Appendix. For the data files and values, please refer to the open platform² and the public GENeSYS-MOD GitLab repository³, where all used data and source code files will be made publically available.

2.2 Updated pan-European results

Although the main drivers for the decarbonization of the energy system differ throughout the scenarios, a generally similar trend within the power system development can be observed, as presented in Figure 2–5. In all scenarios, electricity will primarily be provided by the provision of renewable energy sources. Hereby, onshore wind and solar PV power plants pose to be the major sources of electricity. The highest amount of electricity generated can be seen in the Gradual Development scenario due to the lack of strict demand-side reductions and efficiency increases compared to the other scenarios. In this scenario, the electricity production in 2050 is nearly twice as high as in the base year. The higher demand levels of the non-electricity sectors in Gradual Development also led to the highest amounts of domestically produced hydrogen in the system across all scenarios. In contrast, the three other scenarios see a peak of electricity generation in 2040 and a slight decrease afterward.

² <https://Open.ENTRANCE.eu/open-modelling-platform/>

³ <https://git.tu-berlin.de/genesysmod/genesys-mod-public>

Figure 2-5 European electricity generation (positive) and consumption (negative) until 2050

In the Directed Transition scenario, domestically produced hydrogen increases the overall electricity demand, similar to the Gradual Development scenario, with substantial demand for electricity required for hydrogen production needed as early as 2030. Furthermore, in this scenario, noticeable amounts of electricity will be produced from nuclear power plants in 2050, although the overall share of nuclear energy is diminutive, and a general decrease from 2018 levels can be observed. Although all scenarios see substantial amounts of hydrogen produced, only in Societal Commitment and Techno-Friendly, minuscule amounts of synthetic gas (produced from hydrogen) are utilized in the power sector in 2050. In contrast, electricity storages play a major role in all scenarios, together with the increasing electrification of non-electricity sectors. The latter also is the primary driver for the decrease of overall primary energy demand, as presented in Figure 2-6.

Figure 2-6 European primary energy demand until 2050

Battery-electric vehicles, heat pumps, and most other applications of direct electricity use are often much more energy efficient compared to their conventional alternatives. Therefore, sector coupling in the form of electrification of non-electricity sectors lead to an overall more sustainable energy system. In Societal Commitment, the primary energy demand is further decreased compared to base year levels and the other scenarios. A focus on societal change, change in lifestyle, and adoption of new demand patterns results in meaningful demand reduction across all sectors. Furthermore, although Gradual Development features the least ambitious scenario (2 °C compared to the other 1.5 °C scenarios), the primary energy demand in 2050 is comparable to all other scenarios, being only slightly larger than Directed Transition. However, due to the slower pace of the energy transition, fossil gas has a more predominant role in the energy system until 2040, compared to the more ambitious scenarios. As also depicted in Figure 2-7, only in Techno-Friendly, hydrogen imports from outside of the model boundaries are possible and are, as such, utilized from 2040 onwards. Regarding hydrogen production, in Techno-Friendly, the least amount of hydrogen is domestically produced across all scenarios, peaking already in 2040. Contrary, in Gradual Development, the development of hydrogen production features a less steep slope but sees the highest amount overall in 2050, comparing all scenarios. Whereas the evolution of hydrogen storages is still relatively comparable across the scenarios, the utilization of hydrogen differs substantially. In Gradual Development, Hydrogen is primarily utilized for decarbonizing the freight transport sector, with additional synthetic methane production from hydrogen used in other non-electricity sectors. Direct utilization of hydrogen in the industry sector can be observed in all scenarios, but only in Techno-Friendly, a substantial amount of hydrogen is used for commercial and residential heating as a complement to

heat-pump deployment. As overhead trolley trucks are enabled in Techno-Friendly, the road-based freight transportation sector, can utilize this highly efficient technology for decarbonizing and, as such, hydrogen can be more efficiently consumed in other sectors.

Figure 2-7 Generation (positive) and consumption (negative) of hydrogen in Europe

Comparing the CO₂ emissions in the different scenarios, it can be observed that Societal Commitment and Techno-Friendly feature somewhat similar developments, as presented by Figure 2-8. Both have small amounts of emissions still present in 2035 and nearly complete decarbonization from 2040 onwards. In Techno-Friendly, minuscular amounts of negative emissions are additionally used further to reduce the emissions in the later model periods. In Directed Transition, emission removal technologies are also available but are not utilized. In contrast, this scenario sees the most substantial decrease in emissions in the earlier model periods due to the strict enforcement of efficient emission control policies. Only in Gradual Development, CO₂ emitting technologies play a prevalent role in 2040 and 2045, as in this scenario a 2 °C compatible CO₂-price has been set. Similarly, Gradual Development sees the highest emissions from 2025 onwards across all sectors but still reach net-zero emissions in 2050.

Figure 2-8 Total annual emissions per sector (top) and energy carrier (bottom) until 2050

As implied by the preceding figures and findings, the electrification of non-electricity sectors becomes the most important way to decarbonize those sectors and, thus, will be the primary driver of increasing electricity demand. Across all sectors and scenarios, GENE SYS-MOD results suggest an average electrification rate of 64% in 2050. Overall, the buildings sector sees the highest electrification rate in all scenarios, as heat pumps and electric radiators are cost-efficient technologies for decarbonizing residential and commercial space heat and warm water requirements. In this sector, only minor differences between the scenarios can be observed, with Societal Commitment and Techno-Friendly having a slightly lower electrification rate compared to the other two scenarios. In contrast, the electrification of the transportation sector averages around 43%, apart from Techno-Friendly, which sees a higher rate. Only in this scenario, electric overhead trolley trucks are deployed and, therefore, help to decarbonize the road-based freight transportation services. In the other modes and scenarios, hydrogen or hydrogen-based products (i.e., synthetic fuels) are largely required for either non-road-based transport or long-distance freight transportation. However, although, Techno-Friendly has the highest electrification rate in the transportation sector, it sees the least electrification in the industry sector. In Techno-Friendly, the possibility of low-cost hydrogen imports (and therefore lower costs of hydrogen in general) results in reduced direct electrification of industrial processes in favor of industrial heat generation technologies based on hydrogen or hydrogen-based products.

Figure 2-9 Electrification rate per sector and scenario (grey line represents annual average)

Regarding the development of the interconnectors between the European countries, an increase of transmission capacities until 2050 is common for all scenarios. In the Gradual Development scenario, the speed of the addition of new interconnections is slower in the earlier periods compared to the other scenarios. In 2050, however, Gradual Development sees the overall most interconnection capacities installed of all scenarios. Generally, it can be seen that for Gradual Development, the overall trend of installing transmission capacities correlates with the growth in overall electricity production. For Directed Transition, Societal Commitment, and Techno-Friendly a rather similar network expansion plan can be observed regarding the overall transmission capacities. However, as depicted in Figure 2-10, different interconnectors are preferred in the specific scenarios. For example, in Directed Transition, the connectors France-Switzerland and Switzerland-Italy are expanded the most across all scenarios, whereas in Societal Commitment, Spain-France sees the highest additions in transmission capacities. The Scandinavian interconnection between Sweden and Norway also sees a significant expansion, especially in the Gradual Development scenario, where large offshore wind capacities are constructed in Norway, alongside with transmission expansions – especially to Sweden. The reasons for these expansions are commonly the existence of abundant renewable potentials in neighboring regions, as well as usage of the electricity grid to balance intermittent renewables (in case that there is low availability of wind or solar in one region, the neighboring regions could then pick up this deficiency). More in-depth results on this are shown in Section 3.1.

Figure 2-10 Total transmission capacity of the European energy system (top) and spatial representation of the resulting power grid in 2050 (bottom)

Contrary to the full-hourly dispatch model that has been added to GENeSYS-MOD as described in Chapter 2 2.1, the actual model runs run at a reduced hourly time resolution. For the computation of the Open ENTRANCE scenarios in this Deliverable, a resolution of 72 time steps has been chosen, yielding a reduced consecutive timeseries with 6 representative days of a year, each with 12 2-hour time brackets (see Figure 2-11). This is a necessary trade-off to balance computability, technical level of detail, and temporal resolution. However, these losses of detail are comparatively small, especially for the intended use to generate long-term insights into large-scale energy system models (see also [8] and [9]). For the result generation, GAMS version 35.2, with GUROBI version 9.02 was used. The model computation at this time resolution required about 80GB of RAM and took roughly 65 hours to solve. It has to be noted, however, that lower time resolutions run exponentially faster, using significantly less memory, while offering only marginally different model results on the aggregated pan-European level. Therefore, if only limited computational resources are available, one possibility would be to run the model at a reduced time-resolution and using the hourly dispatch (described in Chapter 2 2.1) to check for feasibility and temporal details of the electricity system, while trading some degree of temporal detail within the energy system optimization.

The dispatch shows the heavy reliance of the resulting European energy system on intermittent renewable energy sources, with hefty solar peaks being used to generate hydrogen via electrolysis, and electricity storages providing backup energy during the night, especially in the winter months.

Figure 2-11 Model-endogenous electricity dispatch with 72 sub-annual time slices (Techno-Friendly, 2050)

2.3 Further processing of GENeSYS-MOD results

The results of GENeSYS-MOD are fully compatible with the Open ENTRANCE scenario explorer and can be accessed from there. The conversion and mappings of the specific GENeSYS-MOD result parameters to the Open ENTRANCE nomenclature is done via an open-source available python package (<https://github.com/Open ENTRANCE/linkages>). The Python package converts the names, does the relevant aggregations, and computes the necessary unit conversions from internal data to Open ENTRANCE nomenclature-compatible data sets. The uploaded data sets can be used by all project partners and external stakeholders, without any further instructions, as the Open ENTRANCE nomenclature was defined by all project partners and follows the well-established IAMC data structure, to accommodate for a common notation for energy system relevant parameters. Furthermore, input data sets of GENeSYS-MOD are also converted and uploaded to the Open ENTRANCE scenario explorer, in order to allow for cross model comparisons and easier links between the models utilized in the Open ENTRANCE project.

Figure 2–12 An example graph of GENE_{SYS}-MOD results in the Open ENTRANCE scenario explorer

In addition, the entire GENE_{SYS}-MOD source code and Open ENTRANCE dataset will be uploaded to the public Git repositories that are part of the open platform. Users from academia, as well as the public and private sectors are invited to use and expand the data, and are encouraged to submit feedback (e.g., new and updated sources, or more detailed regional data) to be considered for inclusion in the public dataset. This enables a community-based improvement of the data by providing both validation and updates in a crowd-sourced manner. Also, the Open ENTRANCE results will be further used in a wide range of research projects, at European, as well as country-level, and therefore serve as a foundation for new research.

3 Selected country-specific scenario results

While the previous chapter presented some results at a Pan-European level, this chapter aims at giving some insights into country-level results that can be obtained with the chosen GENeSYS-MOD model set-up. First, an overview over the entirety of all modeled regions is given, followed by a presentation of selected EU Member States in detail (for this, Germany, France, and Spain have been chosen).

3.1 Overview: European country-specific results

Figure 3–1 displays the regional generation of electricity in 2050 for the Techno-Friendly scenario. The map shows a clear trend towards heavy reliance on solar PV in southern parts of Europe, while the northern parts rely more on wind (and hydropower, where available). Especially the North Sea and Baltic regions see a significant influx of offshore wind generation, given the high full-load hours possible in these regions. Some synthetic methane is used in the electricity system in Techno-Friendly, mostly for peaking and grid-stability reasons, with the absolute vast majority of generation

Figure 3–1 Map of regional power generation in 2050 (Techno-Friendly)

coming from variable renewable energy sources.

Depending on the potentials for these renewable energy sources and the domestic energy needs, some countries become substantial net-exporters of electricity, while others see an increase in net electricity imports (see Figure 3–2). This is also influenced by the model nature, optimizing total system costs across all regions, therefore aiming at a cost-optimal and efficient usage of all available potentials, which then benefits the entire energy system. The expansion of the European electricity grid (as seen in Figure 2–10) also means that these spatially distributed generation capacities can be used to balance out the intermittency of the overall grid to some extent, allowing for benefits of good renewable potentials to be shared with neighbouring countries.

Figure 3–2 Share of domestic electricity generation (average across scenarios)

On an absolute scale, electricity generation rises significantly across all scenarios, mostly due to the

Figure 3–3 Total electricity generation per region (graph shows the sum of all scenarios)

high degree of sector-coupling and direct and indirect electrification. Figure 3–3 shows the distribution of this increase in electricity generation for each European country. While some of the largest electricity-generating countries remain located within that group (e.g., Germany or France), other countries (such as Spain or Turkey) drastically increase their electricity outputs, increasing their share in total generation numbers across Europe. Especially Turkey sees a substantial uptick in electricity generation (an increase of roughly 300% in the Pan-European results), an effect which is further discussed and highlighted in the disaggregated Turkish model presented in chapter 4.1.2.

Figure 3–4 shows some maps for comparison of various model outputs on a country level for the Directed Transition scenario. This Figure also showcases some of the result analyses that are possible and insights that can be generated using GENeSYS-MOD. The upper row starts with three maps, displaying total hydrogen generation per country (left), electricity generation by wind (middle), and PV technologies (right). The bottom row shows the final electricity consumption (excluding for electrolysis, as this is indirectly already shown in the hydrogen generation graph in the top left) on the left, hydrogen & synthetic methane exports in the middle, and hydrogen & synthetic methane imports on the right. The graphs clearly demonstrate that Spain and Turkey become the main suppliers of renewable hydrogen in Europe (Spain mostly through synthetic methane, which is then transported using the existing gas pipeline network, whereas Turkey mostly generated hydrogen which is then transported in the form of liquid hydrogen throughout Eastern and Central Europe). This also shows in the total electricity generation from wind and solar, where these two countries excel, especially with regards to available potentials. As the graph shows, most final electricity (and energy) consumption is concentrated towards Central Europe, with Germany emerging as the main importer of hydrogen throughout Europe.

This differs somewhat when low-cost hydrogen imports from outside of Europe are allowed, as is the case in the Techno-Friendly scenario (the hydrogen import price in Techno-Friendly in 2050 lies at 1.35€ per kg). Then, less hydrogen needs to be produced domestically within Europe, reducing the amount of electricity needed and substantially reduces the quantities of traded hydrogen & synthetic methane within Europe (compare also Figure 2–5 and Figure 2–7). This change in assumption on (global) hydrogen availability also heavily influences the country-level results, which are presented in the following chapter 3.2.

Figure 3-4 Comparison of different model results for the Directed Transition scenario in 2050

3.2 Presentation of selected EU Member States in detail

3.2.1 Germany

Similar to the pan-European results, the transformation of the energy system in Germany, leads to an overall increased consumption and production of electricity. This development is driven by the increased electrification of non-electricity sectors, such as residential and commercial heating, transport, and industry.

Figure 3-5 Electricity generation (top) and consumption (bottom) in Germany

As presented in Figure 3-5, the overall production of electricity ranges from around 880 TWh (Directed Transition) to nearly 1100 TWh (Gradual Development). In all scenarios, a mix of solar PV, onshore wind, and offshore wind, backed up by battery storages and CAES systems becomes the primary provider of electricity. In contrast, the role of natural gas differs substantially between the scenarios. Whereas natural gas plays a more significant role in the Direct Transition scenario as a flexible generator, it is nearly phased out of the electricity system until 2030/2035 in Societal Commitment and Gradual Development. Furthermore, in Techno-Friendly, natural gas utilization in the power sector is substantially reduced until 2025.

The importance of electricity storages for Germany is highlighted in Figure 3-6. Short-term storages, such as batteries, provide electricity to balance the intermittency of solar PV, whereas long-term storages (i.e., CAES or PHS) help to mitigate the inter-seasonality of wind power plants. Additional

biomass generators provide additional backup capacities. The results for the power sector in Germany computed by GENeSYS-MOD showcase an electricity system based on nearly 100% renewables that still is able to fulfill the annual electricity demand on a full-hourly scale. Furthermore, transmission interconnections provide additional flexibility for the system (in the form of imports and exports from neighboring countries) and reduce the necessity of electricity curtailment in specific hours. Nonetheless, over 93% of the annual electricity production comes from variable renewable sources.

Figure 3-6 Hourly electricity dispatch for Germany (months of March and September), using the resulting energy system from GENeSYS-MOD

Germany is the largest economy of the modeled region in the considered scenarios and due to the energy-intensity of its industrial sector, it has a substantial demand for hydrogen electricity. Especially regarding hydrogen, the scenarios highlight that domestic production only plays a role in 2050 for Directed Transition, Gradual Development, and Societal Commitment. In Techno-Friendly, no domestic hydrogen production is deployed and instead, substantial amounts of hydrogen are imported from non-EU countries. The primary share of hydrogen in the other three scenarios is imported from other European countries. The overall demand for hydrogen in Germany ranges from about 675 PJ in Gradual Development to around 1000 PJ in Directed Transition. In Gradual Development, Hydrogen is nearly solely being used for additional decarbonization of the transportation sector, whereas in Techno-Friendly, higher shares of the transportation sector are directly electrified. Furthermore, apart from Gradual Development, significant amounts of hydrogen are used for residential and commercial heating in Germany, with also noticeable amounts utilized in the

industrial sector. It should be noted, however, that a large share of hydrogen (up to 85 PJ) is being used in the form of synthetic methane in industrial applications, which is not shown in this graph.

Figure 3-7 Hydrogen generation and use in Germany

3.2.2 France

Today, the electricity sector in France is mainly dependent on substantial amounts of electricity produced by nuclear power plants. In the calculated results, the existing generators are subsequently replaced by variable renewable energy sources. In Societal Commitment, the electricity sector in 2050 in France is depicted solely without nuclear power plants and only based on renewable energy sources. In this scenario, as well as in Techno-Friendly, the overall electricity production levels stay close to base-year levels or show only smaller increases. For Directed Transition and Gradual Development, overall electricity production increased significantly compared to 2018. However, in all scenarios, electricity generation exceeds the demands from 2030 onwards, such that hydrogen can be produced domestically locally.

Figure 3–8 Electricity generation (top) and consumption (bottom) in France

As depicted in Figure 3–9, the full-hourly dispatch shows that, as significant amounts of nuclear power plants are able to provide baseload together with hydropower plants, fewer storages are installed in France compared to Germany. Still, storages are necessary to provide flexibility and to balance the intermittency and variability of renewable energy sources. Furthermore, the full-hourly dispatch also highlights the importance of interconnectors for designing a secure and stable electricity system. Also, compared to Germany, offshore wind plays only an auxiliary role in the French electricity system, as solar PV and onshore wind power plants are preferred for decarbonizing the power system here.

Figure 3-9 Hourly electricity dispatch for France (months of March and September), using the resulting energy system from GENeSYS-MOD

Different to Germany, most of the utilized hydrogen in France is produced domestically, although small additional amounts are still imported from neighboring countries. Furthermore, in Techno-Friendly, additional amounts are imported from non-EU countries, which even replace the imports from within the European regions in 2050. Overall, most of the hydrogen is being used for decarbonizing the transport sector in Gradual Development, Directed Transition, and Societal Commitment, and only in Techno-Friendly, the buildings sector is using hydrogen in significant amounts.

Figure 3-10 Hydrogen generation and use in France

3.2.3 Spain

With its good potentials for solar PV and onshore wind, Spain becomes a major energy provider in the future European energy system in all scenarios. Excess energy from renewable production is primary used for hydrogen production, as depicted in Figure 3-11. Especially in Directed Transition, as well as in Societal Commitment, the need for increased hydrogen production is the main driver for the substantial growth in energy production as being observed in all scenarios. All scenarios see a phase-out of conventional generators until 2035 and subsequent large-scale additions of solar and wind capacities. In Techno-Friendly, the general efficiency of direct usage of electricity increases and therefore, the overall need for domestically produced hydrogen is reduced, especially as hydrogen imports from non-EU countries are allowed in this scenario.

Figure 3–11 Electricity generation (top) and consumption (bottom) in Spain

The hourly dispatch highlights again the importance of storages for the stability of the power system. Especially, as in Spain solar PV and onshore wind see significant seasonal patterns (compare Figure 3–12). Although already substantial amounts of excess energy are used to produce hydrogen, substantial amounts of curtailed electricity can be observed in the summer months. Also, as only limited conventional generators and hydropower exist in the power system in 2050, additional biomass capacities are installed for backing up the electricity system, but these are only used in specific hours.

Figure 3–12 Hourly electricity dispatch for Spain (months of March and September), using the resulting energy system from GENeSYS-MOD

As already presented in the previous figures, Figure 3–13 highlights the importance of Spain as a possible future key energy provider for Europe. In all scenarios, despite Techno-Friendly, over 800 PJ of hydrogen from electrolysis are produced. Much of this amount is then exported to the European countries directly. Additionally, especially in Gradual Development and Societal Commitment, Hydrogen is used to generate notable amounts of synthetic methane. In contrast to France and Germany, Spain has limited own consumption of hydrogen, most of which is used within the transportation sector in all scenarios. In Techno-Friendly, additional amounts of hydrogen are also used for decarbonizing the residential and commercial heating systems. In Techno-Friendly in 2050, no hydrogen is directly exported and instead additional hydrogen from non-EU countries is imported. Still, even in Techno-Friendly synthetic methane is produced in Spain and exported to other European countries.

Figure 3-13 Hydrogen generation and use in Spain

3.3 Discussion of Insights & Limitations

3.3.1 Relevant insights gained from the updated scenario calculations

- Interconnections are expanded significantly in all scenarios
- Dispatch shows importance of storages -> political targets and constraints should also be expanded to accommodate for the build-up of flexibility options (such as interconnectors and storages)
- Substantial amounts of renewables needed in all scenarios
- Hydrogen
 - Spain, and Turkey become the main hydrogen exporters in Europe, while Germany, France, and Italy import significant amounts of hydrogen and synthetic natural gas
 - -> This indicated a high spatial disparity in hydrogen production and consumption
 - Generally, high amounts of hydrogen are traded between the regions, mostly in the form of liquid hydrogen
 - -> this is due to the model decision to not allow gaseous hydrogen to be used within the existing gas pipeline infrastructure due to viability concerns
 - -> It should therefore be further analyzed what retrofits or pipeline reconstructions would be necessary to trade the required quantities via a pipeline network
- Negative emission technologies are only deployed in small amounts and play no major role

- Conventional generators and biomass in 2050 only used for peak-load (apart from nuclear)
 - Capacity markets for low-carbon generators might be needed to keep them profitable and available

3.3.2 Model limitations & further research potentials

While GENeSYS-MOD has been meaningfully improved with the new version – both with respect to the model source code and mathematical formulation, as well as regarding the new and updated dataset, there are still limitations that need to be kept in mind. Being a linear program, GENeSYS-MOD can offer a great level of technical detail, while still giving relatively high granularity on spatial and temporal dimensions, but at the same time, not all types of decisions can be modeled in a realistic way. Since any fractional investments are allowed, technologies such as overhead trolley trucks (heavily used in the Techno-Friendly scenario due to their energy efficiency) might be seen in a rather optimistic fashion, since the (huge) upfront investment can only be partially represented.

Also, since the model performs a full cost optimization of the entire European energy system with perfect foresight, the generated results have to be taken with some caution, as they cannot (and are not meant to) predict the future but are aimed at generating insights into low-cost pathways for deep decarbonization scenarios within Europe. Other factors, such as political and social barriers (e.g., social acceptance of technology choices), influence of incumbent actors, and geo-political black swan events such as the war in Ukraine cannot be considered in such a setting and instead require outside assumptions on scenario developments.

As a cost-optimizing energy system model, any assumptions regarding cost and technology data heavily influence the modeling results. While all input data points and assumptions have been made to our best ability, it is impossible to fully cover all aspects of every sector in full detail, especially since any data past the current date is by definition uncertain and speculation. To combat such issues, tools like sensitivity analyses and stochastic optimization can and have been applied to identify the correct workings of the model and effects of these issues on model results (compare [10] and [4]).

Also, since GENeSYS-MOD only features a reduced hourly timeseries (instead of running a full hourly computation per year), some effects, especially in the power sector, cannot be fully covered. Since many power sector-specific issues (especially regarding future energy systems with extremely high shares of intermittent renewables) occur at levels between hours and seconds, the rough time resolution of large-scale energy system models such as GENeSYS-MOD can only offer rough outlines of the actual power system, requiring the coupling and validation via other models to check for actual feasibility of the model results (including security of supply aspects).

4 Selected region-specific and local-level scenario results

4.1 GENESYS-MOD: Region-specific results

4.1.1 Norway

The region-specific results for Norway are partly based on the Master thesis "Modeling Multi-sectoral Decarbonization Scenarios for the Norwegian Energy System" [11]. The study for the thesis has been conducted in the winter/spring 2020/2021 with the preliminary results of the pan-European decarbonisation pathway analysis. Hence, the results have been updated with the final version of the Open ENTRANCE dataset for Europe and the new GENeSYS-MOD version from April 2022.

The analysis of Norway has been conducted both for Norway at a country level (one node) and on a more detailed subnational, power-price region level (5 nodes). The disaggregation has been based on available statistical/historic data and when not available proxies build on population, industry locations and land area. All four Open ENTRANCE transition scenarios have been considered for the analysis, both for the aggregate, one node Norway model as well as the disaggregated version. The base year is 2018 and the results computed with GENeSYS-MOD v3.1.

4.1.1.1 Validation of GENeSYS-MOD results for Norway

In 2021, a first through validation process of the input data and results for Norway has been conducted and has been repeated with the final input data and results in April 2022. Values produced by GENeSYS-MOD for Norwegian power capacities, productions, and balance were compared to results from the long-term power market analyses published in October 2021 by the Regulator, NVE [12]. The report models the years 2020 to 2040.

The Regulator's analysis aims to predict the development of the electricity market towards 2040. Hence, the overall objective for this analysis differs from the Open ENTRANCE aim of limiting the global temperature increase to 1.5 and 2 degrees. The results from Open ENTRANCE show an energy system that is much faster de-carbonised than the domestic Norwegian study. The power demand and production from Open ENTRANCE are shown in Figure 4-1.

In the study from the Regulator, they estimate an electricity consumption increase from 138 TWh/year to 174 TWh in 2040. This increase includes a 13 TWh increase in the transport sector, 7 TWh for hydrogen production from electrolysis and a 16 TWh increase in industry consumption. The Regulator assumes 6 TWh in decreased consumption due to energy efficiency measures. The high increase in the industry sector is based on the many plans for new power consuming industries, e.g.,

data centers, in Norway. There is a rather high uncertainty, regarding which and how many of these plans will be realized. Norway has a significant potential for energy efficiency in both industry and buildings. Presently, Norway has a very high share of direct electric heating and large-scale deployment of heat pumps can significantly reduce power consumption. [13] finds that maximum use of heat-pumps gives a potential for decrease in power consumption of 16 TWh/year. In addition, there is a potential for better isolation of houses.

The base year for the final Open ENTRANCE scenarios is 2018 and all scenarios start with the same base year electricity consumption of 142 TWh. In all scenarios, except Gradual Development (which only reaches the 2 degree target), a decrease in electricity demand towards 2050 is assumed. All scenarios see a drop in the nearer future (driven by expected high fossil fuel prices (especially gas)), followed by an increase back to start levels towards 2040 and then again, a decrease. This is a different development as assumed by the regulator, resulting from two main differences in the scenario work: first, the regulator accounts for new industry that is likely to be established while the Open ENTRANCE scenarios do not specifically include new industry developments and second the Open ENTRANCE scenarios are ways to a net-zero future, while the regulators scenario is aiming at trying to mirror the most likely future development. The Regulators estimated 13 TWh of electricity demand increase in the transport sector, is then very much in line with the increase modelled in the Open ENTRANCE scenarios, which ranges between 11 to 14TWh for the four scenarios (increase to 20240). In the Open ENTRANCE scenarios industry demand of electricity decreases significantly, in strong but expected contrast with what the Regulator assumes. The new demand created by hydrogen production from electrolysis shows to be similar between the Regulators predictions of around 7 TWh and the OpenENTRANCE scenario results of between 4 and 8 TWh.

Figure 4-1 Electricity production and use for Norway from the aggregated vs the disaggregate version

The Regulator assumes an increase in production from 158 TWh annually in 2021 to 186 in 2040. In 2021 the production is composed of 138 TWh hydro power, 18 TWh wind power and 2 TWh “other thermal”. In 2040 the Regulator assumes that the mix is changed to 149 TWh hydro power production, 21 TWh onshore wind, 7 TWh offshore wind, 7 TWh PV production and 2 TWh “other thermal”.

All Open ENTRANCE scenarios show a drastic increase in production in Norway, mainly driven by increase in demand outside Norway. Directed Transition and Techno-Friendly show production levels around 200 TWh in 2040 increasing further towards 2050. Both scenarios show large deployment of offshore wind, producing well above 20 TWh/year. Additional onshore wind power is restrained for Norway in the Open ENTRANCE scenarios in the near future. This has been done, to account for the actual situation in Norway, where no new permissions for onshore wind farms have been granted and it has further been decided that no new onshore wind allowances will be awarded in the near future. This political decision follows public opinion in Norway, which has been dominated by significant public resistance for further onshore wind farm development. Societal commitment shows a production increase closer to the one modelled by the Regulator and has no offshore wind power in the production mix in the future. Production from hydro power in the Open ENTRANCE scenarios is assumed to increase to around 150 TWh in 2040, in line with the Regulators assumptions. Production from PV production is also similar to what the Regulator expects for all scenarios, except Societal Commitment (only 2,5 TWh in 2040).

4.1.1.2 Disaggregation of Norway

Since March 2010, Norway has been split into five electric bidding zones. The zones are defined as Southeast Norway (NO1), Southwest Norway (NO2), Mid-Norway (NO3), Northern Norway (NO4), and West Norway (NO5) [14]. These zones are shown in Figure 4–2. The five regions have very different characteristics regarding amount of demand, type of demand, production capacities and potentials, and resource availability. To account for these differences, it is useful to look at the five regions separately when modelling future energy system developments for Norway. In a disaggregation exercise, the Open ENTRANCE scenarios for Norway were split into those five bidding zones. As Norway has close to 100% electric heating, the power sector plays already today an important role in the electricity system and offers the opportunity for power demand reductions by heat pumps rather than constituting a new load. There is also some statistical data available per bidding zone as well as the long-term market analyses from the Regulator and the TSO (Statnett).

Figure 4–2 Bidding zones in the Norwegian power system [14]

The factors population, location of large industries and land area are used for disaggregation of Norwegian domestic data. In a report from the Regulator [15], a similar approach is used for disaggregating Norwegian country level data into the five bidding zones. The Regulator argues that due to the unavailability of good and open data on the geography of the building stock and the vehicle park/transport services, the population shares can be used to disaggregate parameters dependent

on building area, such as residential heating and power demand, and that the same shares can be used to disaggregate transportation parameters, such as mobility demand.

Table 4–1 Population, industry and land area per bidding zone used for the disaggregation of Norway [11]

Region	Population (%)	Industry (%)	Land Area (%)
NO1	42	5	15
NO2	24	28	14
NO3	14	32	23
NO4	9	19	41
NO5	11	17	7

Similar assumptions as those used in Regulator’s report were used to disaggregate most of the parameters, see Table 4–1 for the shares used. Power, mobility, and residential heating demands were disaggregated based on population. Industrial heating demands were disaggregated based on the location of large industries. Base year production and capacity parameters related to residential heating were disaggregated based on population, while those related to industrial heating were disaggregated based on the location of industry. Parameters concerning resources and resource potentials were disaggregated based on land area. Power trade capacity values were set to current net transmission capacities. Trade routes between regions were set to the distances, measured in kilometres between the approximate geographic centres of each region. Regional onshore wind potentials are taken from a report conducted by SINTEF [16]. The potentials in the report are based on the locations of current and future onshore wind projects. In addition, factors such as wind conditions and geographical terrain are considered. Oil and gas resources were disaggregated using data provided by Norwegian Petroleum (NPD) for resource allocation in each sea on the Norwegian coast [17]. It was assumed that there are no resources in NO1, that the Barents Sea resources are in NO4, that the Norwegian Sea resources are in NO3, and that the North Sea resources are split evenly between NO2 and NO5. Similarly, the CCS potentials were disaggregated using data from the NPD [18]. No offshore wind production potential was allocated to NO1, as there is no offshore wind potential in that region. The same solar and wind profiles have been used for the one region Norway model as for all regions in the disaggregated version.

4.1.1.3 Insights from the results per power bidding price zone in Norway

The disaggregated results show that consistently, through all scenarios, NO2 has the highest power capacities installed and most electricity produced, while NO1 and NO4 have the lowest capacity and production numbers across all scenarios. All regions’ electricity production numbers are highly dominated by hydro power, except NO3 in the Gradual development scenario. NO3 has large offshore wind potentials and with generally much higher demand in Gradual Development, there is a need to exploit those. Gradual development shows also a much higher solar share in NO4 (Northern Norway) than any of the other regions and scenarios, partly explainable by its very large land area and the use

of the same profiles for solar power across all Norwegian regions, and that offshore wind potential are not used, since the deep waters off the coastline only allow for floating offshore, which is associated with significantly higher costs. Figure 4–3 shows electricity production in the five Norwegian spot price regions for 2050 for the four Open ENTRANCE scenarios.

Figure 4–3 Electricity production in the five Norwegian spot price regions for 2050 for the four Open ENTRANCE scenarios

Figure 4–1 shows the differences in electricity production observed when contrasting the one region model to the disaggregated version. While the installed hydro power capacities are used to its maximum in both versions, resulting in equal production numbers for both scenarios and regions, production from offshore wind is higher across the different scenarios in the aggregated version as compared to the disaggregated version. The system in the disaggregated version also uses less storage across the different regions and scenarios, see Figure 4–4. The use of electrolysis to produce hydrogen is an interesting aspect of the scenario results that show considerable differences, when looking at the results obtained by the aggregated version versus the disaggregated version. There is in general more hydrogen production in Norway in the disaggregated model and it is used to a much higher extend and share for the transport sector. Techno-Friendly is the only scenario that allows for imports of hydrogen from outside the EU and in the aggregated version, Norway makes use of this considerably from 2040 onwards in the aggregated model version. In the disaggregated version

hydrogen is also imported but to a much smaller extend. Interesting is also the observation that hydrogen is only used in buildings to a considerable extend in the Techno-Friendly scenario, in all other scenarios it is mainly used for transport.

Figure 4-4 - Hydrogen production and use in Norway for the aggregated vs the disaggregated model

4.1.1.4 Discussions of insights and further improvements

Our modelling results show considerable electricity production increase, despite the fact that the four scenarios developed in Open ENTRANCE do not show demand increases in Norway. This is to a large extend due to that no new industry demand is included in the demand developments and that the floor heating sector in Norway is already almost 100% electrified today. Most new capacity additions to the power sector show to be in the offshore wind sector, since new future onshore-wind capacity expansion is limited, in-line with political decisions in the recent past. Norway shows hence to contribute to reach the EU's ambitious latest goals of reaching several 100 GW of offshore wind installations within the next decade. Hydrogen, currently only produced on technology-testing scales, is becoming a notable part of the energy only after 2030 and used for both transport and a flexibility deliverer.

The natural next step to refine the disaggregated model further is the use of regional resource data for both wind and solar. Since especially offshore-wind is expected to grow significantly and there potentially are notable difference between the wind profiles of the different regions, this is an important further improvement. For the Norwegian case, a further consideration regards he

assessment if a new technology for point source heating with biomass could help to better assess the potential to well describe and efficiently use already established alternative heating infrastructure.

4.1.2 Turkey

The analysis for Turkey is carried out both at aggregated and regionally disaggregated levels. In the disaggregated model, the country is analyzed using 12 subregions in NUTS level 1. Figure 4-5 provides the regionally disaggregated map of Turkey. The disaggregation process is based on factors such as the population, industrial production, offshore/onshore potential and land area of each region. The transition scenarios, namely Directed Transition (DT), Societal Commitment (SC), Gradual Development (GD), and Techno Friendly (TF) are employed for the analysis, and the results are obtained using GENeSYS-MOD v3.0. The base year is assumed to be 2015 and the analysis is extended until 2050. The results are summarized in the following section.

Figure 4–5 Regional disaggregation for Turkey at NUTS level 1

4.1.2.1 Disaggregation Process

There are some similarities between the disaggregation process for Turkey and Norway. Please refer therefore to Section 4.1.1 and [19] regarding the methodology, whereas this section focuses on other major issues that arose throughout the disaggregation process for the GENeSYS-MOD Turkey model application at NUTS level 1.

Initial Setup

We have followed the instructions in the GENeSYS-MOD Quick-Start Guide [20], Technical Guide [21] and Data Documentation [22] to perform the addition of a new region to the GENeSYS-MOD v3.0 model. Since there is no detailed disaggregation process described in the guide, several issues arose during this setup process:

There is little or no guidelines about which data input files (EXCEL files as well as worksheets within them) have to be modified in order to add a new region to the model. The data files and calculations within them are not clear. For example:

- In scenario input data files for different scenarios, it is not fully clear which sheets have to be modified. Also, it is not sufficiently explained how to modify the sheets in order to define a new region.
- The calculations for some sheets need to be more clearly explained to properly add a new region (i.e., regarding the modal split) in these scenario specific input data files.
- There are no references for hourly time series data. A section on where and how these data are obtained would be helpful.
- The description of some technologies in time series data and their relations with each other is not clear. This could be improved upon.

This process has mostly been achieved through trial & error. Feedbacks from the team at TU Berlin has been very useful. However, it needs to be noted that without proper guidance, it is challenging for a novice user to modify the GENeSYS-MOD model, i.e., both GAMS files and EXCEL input data files to achieve disaggregation.

To overcome the issues, we first set up a model encompassing twelve regions based on NUTS level 1 for Turkey. These twelve regions were added to all worksheets that have a regional dimension and entries for “TR” (the Alpha-2 code for Turkey). The model parameters have been set in a way similar to Norway's disaggregation process (see Section 4.1.1 and [19]).

Following, the data that was provided in the original model data files has been updated and disaggregated according to the following regional data on population, industrial production, onshore wind production, land area, and offshore wind potentials (see Table 4–2).

Table 4–2 Population, industry, wind potential, and land area per zone

	Key B	Key C	Key D	Key E	Key F
	Population	Industry	Onshore Wind	Land Area	Offshore wind
TR1	18.61%	29.34%	6.47%	0.84%	0.00%
TR2	4.30%	5.36%	22.84%	4.67%	78.02%
TR3	12.88%	13.35%	26.51%	8.40%	0.00%
TR4	9.52%	16.85%	7.82%	9.75%	0.00%
TR5	9.71%	10.66%	4.48%	4.72%	0.00%
TR6	12.75%	8.27%	15.93%	16.34%	3.76%
TR7	4.95%	3.39%	8.91%	7.34%	0.00%
TR8	5.72%	3.14%	4.60%	11.76%	18.22%
TR9	3.27%	1.87%	0.21%	9.68%	0.00%
TRA	2.79%	0.79%	0.00%	8.96%	0.00%
TRB	4.86%	1.75%	0.58%	7.84%	0.00%
TRC	10.65%	5.23%	1.66%	9.71%	0.00%

However, some issues arose regarding certain limits within the scenario files that caused infeasibilities. Detecting them required an option (e.g., IIS 1) in GAMS CPLEX or GUROBI solvers. Unfortunately, in some scenarios, the error-finding process was very time-consuming. Specifically, if one cannot solve multiple large-scale models in parallel, the debugging process takes an extensive amount of time. Solving problems in a serial manner is simply not feasible, since a model with 488 hourly steps and 12 regions of Turkey including the rest of EU regions require more than 24GB of memory. A computing server with a higher memory capacity (in our case 160 GB RAM) is recommended to allow up to 4-5 disaggregated models to be solved in parallel.

4.1.2.2 Time series data for disaggregated Turkish regions

We have employed the renewables.ninja website to collect wind and solar PV time series data (i.e., capacity factors for each hour in a year). Different than most EU countries, there is no published hourly wind or solar PV capacity factor data for Turkey on this website, nor it has any regional disaggregation at NUTS level 1 or 3. Only point data is available, which requires coordinates (in longitude and latitude) for each potential location. Hence, an R code has been employed to obtain longitude and latitude data for Turkey at NUTS level 1 and 3.

In order to do so, we first used the shape data file for the EU (available at this [link](#)) and then located the centroids for each polygon (of each NUTS level 1 & 3) in this shape file. We have used several R packages, specifically the `sf` package, to encode spatial vector data. Other packages are for data

manipulation and visualization/tabulation have also been used (the R codes and instructions are available on GENE SYS-MOD-Turkey [GitHub](#) repository). We then added the centroid of each polygon as a separate geometry column and then filtered the Turkish NUTS level 1 (regional) and 3 (province) regions. Finally, we visualized the centroids and all regions on the following map:

Figure 4-6 Centroids and regions in NUTS level

We have used the tool `ninja_automator.r` that is available on [Github](#) and used the coordinates of centroids of polygons for NUTS levels 1 and 3 to gather the solar PV and wind time series data from the renewables.ninja website (the Github page of `ninja.renewables` has the necessary information, but there is an hourly data gathering limit of 50 queries, i.e., 50 locations at once). For offshore wind data, we have used the data on offshore wind potential in Turkey from the literature, with the first 11 locations selected from [23] and the last 4 locations being selected from [24].

1. Bandırma (TR2)
2. Bozcaada (TR2)
3. Gökçeada (TR2)
4. Burhaniye (TR2)
5. Saros (TR2)
6. Dikili (TR3)
7. Karaburun (TR3)
8. Karasu (TR4)
9. Antalya (TR6)
10. Mersin (TR6)

11. Bafra1 (TR8)
12. Bafra2 (TR8)
13. Inebolu (TR8)
14. Sinop1 (TR8)
15. Sinop2 (TR8)

Then, representative offshore points for these locations were selected from the renewables.ninja website and wind capacity factors have been downloaded. These factors were then averaged for each NUTS level 1 region.

These efforts, however, do not complete the hourly onshore wind, offshore wind, and solar PV time series data required for GENeSYS-MOD, which uses multiple categories of each technology within each region, differentiating between optimal (opt), average (avg), and below average (inf) locations. The values in parentheses show the multipliers for capacity factors we have used for each sub technology:

Solar PV: inf (0.7), avg (0.85), opt (1)

Wind Onshore: inf (0.7), avg (1), opt (0.85)

Wind Offshore: shallow (0.85), deep (0.7) and transitional (1)

Moreover, there are other factors that need to be considered, however, we have no data sources for run-of-river Hydro (RoR) capacity factors at NUTS Level 1 for Turkey. Load data is also only available at the aggregated level. Therefore, we have used the Turkey data currently available in the GENeSYS-MOD database at the aggregated level and used them for all regions in the rest of the hourly time series dataset.

4.1.2.3 *Model results*

The aggregated and disaggregated level results differ for many of the scenarios. Table 4-3 shows the notable differences. Minor differences are also observed for the power dispatch levels in the DT scenario. PHEV and PHEV (bio) levels are not observed in the TF scenario in the aggregated model results. Similar differences are observed for freight transport, residential heat, industrial heat, and hydrogen production and use. Emission levels reach zero by 2040 in the disaggregated model results for TF, GD, and SC scenarios, whereas the emissions in the aggregated model results for TF, GD, and SC scenarios are reaching zero only after 2040.

Table 4–3 The notable differences between aggregated and disaggregated model results

	Disaggregated to subregions	Aggregated
Electricity Generation	Photovoltaic generation increases and no Offshore wind capacity is added	More Onshore wind capacity is observed
Dispatch	Minor differences in DT	
Passanger Transport	PHEV and PHEV (bio) are used in TF scenario	PHEV and PHEV (bio) are not used in TF scenario
Freight Transport	Rail [Conv] values are lower comparing to other scenarios	BEV is not used in TF scenario
Building Heat	Natural gas is decreasing more in GD, SC, and TF; it is phased out 5 years before the aggregated	No direct electric usage in SC scenario
Industrial Heat	Natural gas shows differences in 2035 in TF scenarios; Hydrogen usage is different for both	
Hydrogen Production & Use		No Hydrogen for power generation in SC and TF scenarios
Emission	Emissions reach to zero at 2040 in TF, GD and SC scenarios	Emissions exist in building at 2040 in TF, GD and SC scenarios

4.1.2.3.1 Power production by regions

Figure 4–7 shows the power production in Turkey in 2050 for all scenarios. In all scenarios, significant hydro resources are located in eastern and southeastern regions. Natural gas-based generation resources are usually located in western regions, but are no longer utilized by 2050. The coal-based generation resources are located in central regions as they are located close to coal mines. The solar radiation levels are better in southern regions and wind availability is especially high in northwestern regions, and hence solar and wind production for 2050 occurs mostly in these regions. In all scenario results, renewables mostly replace fossil fuels as early as 2030. The majority of power generation is provided from solar PV in 2050 in all scenarios, while the hydro resources are still significantly used. On the other hand, there is a significant capacity of onshore wind in Northwestern regions while offshore wind sees no meaningful usage.

Figure 4-7 Power production in Turkey in 2050

4.1.2.3.2 Power production by scenarios

The detailed demand and supply distribution at aggregated and disaggregated levels provide important findings. Figure 4-8 provides the details for power production for both aggregated and disaggregated model results. The solar PV generation in the disaggregated model is significantly higher than in the aggregated model, while wind generation is substantially reduced. The main reason is the increase in the new capacity investments for solar PV technologies until 2050 in all scenarios. On the other hand, onshore wind capacity increases until 2040, stabilizes by 2045, and declines a bit by 2050. The existing hydropower resources are already widely used in Turkey and the results show that no significant capacity is added. The trend for installed storage capacities is rising and it is found that there is an upward trend until 2050. The use of fossil fuels in the electricity sector, including coal and natural gas, is phased out by 2030 in the GD, SC, and TF scenarios, while a small portion of natural gas is used in the DT scenario by 2030. The demand for electrolysis, industry, and end-use of electricity (e.g., in the form of appliances) are the main components until 2050 and keep rising until 2040, after which the electrolysis and industry demands stay constant. Albeit the fact that final (end-use) demand is also rising, the trend is within expected intervals. The demand for transport is significant in SC, lower in TF, and almost identical in the GD and DT scenarios.

Figure 4-8 Power generation & use for aggregated and disaggregated model results

The results for the disaggregated model look somewhat different. The capacity for solar PV increases until 2040 in all scenarios and stays constant afterwards. A similar trend is observed for onshore wind, where the capacity increases until 2030 and stays constant afterwards. The hydropower resources are already widely used in Turkey and the results show that not much capacity is added, since significant amounts of existing potentials are already being used. The trend for storage is rising and it is shown that the capacity is increasing until 2050, while a small portion of the generation is provided by biomass. The demand for electrolysis and industry are the main components until 2050 and they keep rising until 2040 and stay constant afterwards. The final energy demand is an exogenous input and therefore similar to the aggregated model. Also following the aggregated model results, the demand for transport is significant in SC, lower in TF, and almost identical in GD and DT.

4.1.2.3.3 Hydrogen production and use by scenarios

Figure 4-9 shows hydrogen production and use for the aggregated and disaggregated scenarios. Hydrogen production reaches a significant level in 2030, and an accelerated production and usage by 2035. The major increases in solar PV capacity in the disaggregated model lead to more opportunities for hydrogen production through electrolysis. Hence, more hydrogen production is observed in disaggregated model. The capacity addition is different across the scenarios. The most significant increase is observed in GD, while the least increase is observed in SC scenario. The DT and TF scenarios are very similar. The demand for hydrogen is significantly allocated to transport sector

followed by industry, buildings, and other sectors. The demand in the disaggregated scenario is different, however: while the demand from transport is still significant, the share of demand from other sectors differs considerably.

Figure 4-9 Hydrogen production & use for aggregated and disaggregated model results

Discussions

The aggregated and disaggregated model results show significant differences. However, the dominance of solar PV and wind resources are obvious for both models and for all scenarios. They keep rising until 2040 and reach a point of saturation afterwards. Coal and natural gas phase-outs in the power sector are observed around 2030. The new capacity allocations are observed in the power production map of Turkey in 2050 (Figure 4-7). On the other hand, the demand for hydrogen will increase significantly by 2040.

Hydrogen production and use also provides important insights. Increasing solar PV capacity with lower capacity factor allows for more hydrogen production in Turkey. Significantly more solar PV capacity is installed in the disaggregated model due to regional availability (i.e., capacity factors). The demand for hydrogen mainly comes from the transportation sector.

More comparative model results (aggregated versus disaggregated) can be found in the Appendix, where figures for the power dispatch, power capacity, passenger transport, freight transport, building heat, industrial heat, emissions, and primary energy demand are presented. The figures are self-explanatory and evident for the discussions in this section on power generation and hydrogen production and use.

4.2 Example: Downscaling of the Austrian Residential Heat Demand

Note that essential parts of the content of the study presented in this Section 4.2 has already been published in the following journal, which acknowledges the support of the Open ENTRANCE project:

[25] S. Zwickl-Bernhard, D. Huppmann, A. Golab, H. Auer: "Disclosing the heat density of district heating in Austria in 2050 under the remaining European CO₂ budget of the 1.5°C climate target", *Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks*, 23 May 2022, 100775, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.segan.2022.100775>.

4.2.1 Objective of the study

The core objective of the following study is to demonstrate a method for further downscaling of country-specific GENeSYS-MOD decarbonization scenarios of the heating sector to the community levels serving end-users in 2050. In particular, the downscaling exercise considers the highly efficient and local use of sustainable heat sources in district heating (e.g., geothermal sources, co-firing synthetic gas and hydrogen in cogeneration plants, and large-scale waste utilization). In addition, the topography of district heating networks is of particular importance and plays a crucial role in the presented downscaling method. This allows estimates of realistic decarbonized district heating networks in 2050 to be obtained, which can be compared with existing network. Thereby, the heat density of district heating networks serves as a comparative indicator and permits a rough estimation of the changes needed for district heating networks considering the 1.5°C and 2.0°C climate target.

An Austrian case study is conducted, downscaling the cost-effective results of the heating sector in 2050 from the large numerical energy system model GENeSYS-MOD, from the country to the community/local administrative unit levels. In general, GENeSYS-MOD exhibits a focus on generic heat supply options based on primary energy sources, rather than specific local excess heat sources that is in general the fundamental idea of district heating. Accordingly, this study can be seen as an attempt for a stress test applying GENeSYS-MOD's heat supply in the context of district heating.

4.2.2 Method applied in the study

Building upon the amount of district heating obtained by the aggregate model GENeSYS-MOD, the downscaling method applied consists of a simplified optimization model, which computes the amount of district heating at the local administrative unit (LAU; i.e. community) level. For overview reasons, we will not present the mathematical model of the optimization and refer to the original paper [25]. The objective function of the model maximizes the heat density per community and in the immediate vicinity, taking into account all factors that determine the net settlement area.

The optimization model allocating the amount of district heating to the LAU level does not necessarily ensure that obtained heat densities of district heating networks reach the benchmark of 10 GWh/km² being assumed in this work. Consequently, below it is explained in detail how the optimal values of

district heating at the LAU level are further processed resulting in heat densities of district heating higher than the benchmark value. The developed workflow is as follows:

- Starting with the optimal amount of district heating at the LAU level obtained from the optimization model.
- Identification all LAUs that do not achieve the required heat density benchmark value of 10 GWh/km².
- For each of those LAUs, the heat density of district heating within the corresponding NUTS3 region and thus network level is calculated.
- In case that the heat density reaches values higher than the benchmark at the NUTS3 level, the supply using district heating remains since LAUs are then connected to or in the surrounding area of high heat density areas.
- Otherwise, the amount of district heating is set to zero as no economic viability can be expected there due to lower achieved heat densities than the benchmark.

Finally, steps 1 to 5 allow to calculate implemented district heating under the condition that either the local heat density at the LAU or the network heat density at the NUTS3 level achieves the assumed heat density benchmark value of 10 GWh/km².

4.2.3 Test bed description

As a starting point for the downscaling exercise of the residential and commercial heating sector in Austria in 2050, the heat generation mix for the four different Open ENTRANCE scenarios (Directed Transition, Societal Commitment, Techno-friendly, and Gradual Development) is used (see Table 4–4).

Table 4–4 Heat generation by source in Austria in 2020 and the four different GENeSYS-MOD decarbonization scenarios in 2050 [25].

Generation by source in TWh	obtained from GENeSYS-MOD				
	2020	2050			
	-	DT	SC	TF	GD
Biomass	13.00	3.37	3.37	3.37	3.37
Direct electric	4.10	2.13	1.98	1.53	1.81
Geothermal	0	2	2	2	2
Natural gas (fossil)	43.67	0	0	0	0
Heat pump (air)	11.37	22.73	15.71	25.96	9.68
Heat pump (ground)	0	17.50	19.47	4.69	19.21
Hydrogen	0	1.03	2.18	7.43	8.65
Oil	0.66	0	0	0	0
Synthetic gas	0	0.36	1.35	2.79	5.35
Waste	1.2	2	2	2	2
Total	74.0	51.12	48.06	49.77	52.07
Rel. reduction compared to 2020	-	-31%	-35%	-33%	-30%
District heating		16.75	15.38	27.20	22.84

In the following analysis, the naming convention of heat sources/generation technologies from GENeSYS-MOD is essentially followed to ensure consistency between aggregated (i.e., downscaling input values) and local (i.e., downscaling output values) levels. Nevertheless, we introduced the heat sources waste and geothermal that were initially not included in the list of heat sources from Open ENTRANCE results. We separated waste as part of biomass and geothermal from heat pump (ground-sourced) heat generation using estimates from national Austrian studies to complement the GENeSYS-MOD results. Note that the values obtained from GENeSYS-MOD do not explicitly include district heating, which is why its 2020's value in Table 2 cannot be specified. The total heat generation (and thus total heat demand) is significantly reduced when comparing the values of 2020 and 2050. The heat demand reduction varies between -30% and -35% and is highest in the Societal Commitment scenario. District heating (bottom row in

Table 4–4) describes the amount of heat generation used for district heating. In this work, the assumption is made that geothermal, hydrogen, synthetic gas, waste, and half of the total heat generation by heat pumps (air-sourced) are used in district heating. Therefore, we claim that (see [25] for more details and citations in this context)

1. geothermal and waste as renewable heat sources contribute to the decarbonization of heat supply by the integration into district heating;
2. the limited amounts of synthetic gas and hydrogen are preferably used in district heating (i.e., co-firing in cogeneration plants) if they supply (residential and commercial or low-temperature) heat demands.
3. half of the cost-optimal heat supply of heat pumps (air-sourced) of the aggregate model GENeSYS-MOD are used in district heating through implementation of large-scale heat pumps. Accordingly, heat pumps (air-sourced) significantly contribute to supply decarbonized district heating networks.

4.2.4 Results and discussion

In the following result presentation, the focus is on the mix of heat sources/generation technologies and district heating in the four different Open ENTRANCE scenarios. First, the heat supply of a representative Austrian NUTS3 region is shown in detail. Building upon, heat supply in an urban and a rural LAU/district is compared. Next, the obtained heat densities of district heating networks are presented. Finally, the results of district heating are synthesized and indications are provided that could be returned into more aggregate models, such as GENeSYS-MOD, in the sense of a feedback loop.

Heat supply in a representative NUTS3 region in 2050

This section presents the results of the NUTS3 region Salzburg and Surroundings (AT323). Figure 4–10 shows the most relevant results in this region on LAU/district level for the four different Open ENTRANCE scenarios. District heating supplies heat demands in 5 different LAUs/communities. In particular, the LAUs are in the surrounding area of Salzburg city (marked by the star). The remaining LAUs in the NUTS3 region are supplied decentralized/on-site. Details of the heat sources that supply heat demands in LAUs with district heating and with decentralized/on-site heat systems are presented further below. The amount of district heating varies between 1.045 and 1.132 TWh per year (Figure 4–10, top right). The highest value is achieved in the *Gradual Development* scenario, since this is the scenario with the lowest heat demand reduction. The heat density of district heating in the 5 LAUs is shown in Figure 4–10 bottom right. The highest heat density is achieved in Salzburg city and reaches approximately 30 GWh/km² in each scenario. The comparable low heat densities in two of the five LAUs (marked by rectangle and plus) is discussed further below.

Figure 4–10 District heating and decentralized/on-site heat supply in the representative NUTS3 region (incl. LAUs/communities) 'Salzburg and Surroundings' (AT323) [25].

Comparison of heat supply in urban and rural LAUs/community

Building upon the so-far presented results of the NUTS3 region Salzburg and Surroundings, this section shows the heat sources/generation technologies supplying heat demands in an urban and in a rural LAU/community. We use Salzburg city (urban community) and Abtenau (rural community) as representative LAUs. Figure 4–11 shows the mix of heat sources supplying heat demands in both LAUs. The geographical location is shown on the top left in Figure 4–11. In Salzburg city (marked by the orange edge), district heating supplies heat demands, which uses large-scale heat pumps (air-sourced), hydrogen, synthetic gas, and waste as heat sources/generation technologies. High shares of district heating particularly are generated by large-scale heat pumps (air) and using hydrogen. In contrast, the heat supply in the rural district Abtenau uses small-scale heat pumps (air), heat pumps (ground-sourced), biomass, and direct electric heating systems. Among all four scenarios, high shares of heat demands are supplied by heat pumps (air- and ground-sourced). However, the share of each technology varies to some extent significantly, which becomes evident when comparing exemplarily the *Techno-Friendly* and *Gradual Development* scenario. In the *Techno-Friendly*, small-scale heat pumps (air-sourced) are the dominant heat source, whereby heat pumps (ground-sourced) supply high shares of heat demands in the *Gradual Development* scenario.

Figure 4–11 Comparison of heat supply in an urban LAU with district heating ('Salzburg' city) and in a rural LAU with no district heating ('Abtenau') [25].

Heat densities of district heating in LAUs in 2050

Figure 4–12 below shows the heat density of district heating at the LAU/district level in 2050 for the four different Open ENTRANCE scenarios. Particularly, the values of LAU's heat densities are sorted in descending order indicating those LAUs/communities that do not reach the required heat density of economic viability, which is assumed to be 10 GWh/km². Exemplarily, in the *Directed Transition* scenario, 107 LAUs with district heating are found. In this scenario, the highest heat density is 43.17 GWh/km². 2 of the 5 LAUs in the NUTS3 region Salzburg and Surroundings are highlighted, namely, Salzburg city (marker by the star in Figure 4–10) and Anif (marked by the rectangle in Figure 4–10). Both LAUs are part of the same district heating network as already illustrated in the left subfigure in Figure 4–10. Accordingly, the appearance of heat densities below the assumed threshold/benchmark for economic viability can be argued as those LAUs are connected to high heat density areas. The distribution of heat density values remains mostly the same between the four different scenarios. For the sake of clarity, explicit annotations are omitted in the three (smaller) scenario subfigures at the bottom.

Figure 4–12 Heat density values at the LAU level in the four different scenarios in descending order [25].

Geographical localization of district heating in 2050

In the following section the focus is on those LAUs with lower heat densities than assumed to be required for economic viability for district heating and their geographical location in respect to other district heating supply areas. As indicated in Figure 4–12, LAUs with low heat densities can be quite justified in case that they are located in the surrounding area of high heat density areas (e.g., Salzburg city and Anif). However, other LAUs that do not achieve the required heat density benchmark (of 10 GWh/km²) and at the same time are not closely located to high heat density areas are unlikely to be implemented. Accordingly, Figure 4–13 shows the heat map of district heating in Austria at the LAU level under the requirement that district heating achieves the required heat density benchmark within NUTS3 regions in the *Directed Transition* scenario. As previously mentioned, the model basically decides to supply heat demands in 105 LAUs by district heating. 63 of them already achieved heat densities higher than the benchmark value. The heat map in Figure 4–13 still shows 68 LAUs since 5 are closely located to high heat density areas and thus achieve in total the benchmark (at the NUTS3 level).

Figure 4–13 Heat density of district heating in the Directed Transition scenario in 2050 achieving the required heat density benchmark value of 10 GWh/km² at the NUTS3 level [25].

Accordingly, district heating is unlikely to be implemented in 37 LAUs. Table 4–5 summarizes the results for district heating in the four different Open ENTRANCE scenarios. It shows that as a result of the heat density benchmark at the NUTS3 level, the share of implemented district heating varies between 74 and 90%. In particular, this means exemplarily that in the *Techno-Friendly* scenario, 74% of the assumed heat supply using district heating leads to heat density values higher than 10 GWh/km². In view of the previous assumptions that 50% of heat pumps (air-sourced) are used in district heating, this results in implemented shares between 23% and 40%, whereby the highest share is achieved in the *Directed Transition* scenario.

Table 4–5 Overview of district heating supplying heat demands in 2050 in the four different scenarios [25].

Results in the four scenarios	DT	SC	TF	GD
District Heating (from GENeSYS-MOD) in TWh	16.75	15.38	27.20	22.84
LAUs with district heating (from downscaling)	105	105	107	105
- of which with more than 10 GWh/km ²	63	57	62	64
- of which with less than 10 GWh/km ²	42	60	45	41
LAUs with district heating (10 GWh/km ² at NUTS3)	68	66	68	68
District heating (10 GWh/km ² at NUTS3) in TWh	14.57	13.08	20.09	20.62
- share in district heating from GENeSYS-MOD in %	87	85	74	90
- share of large-scale heat pumps (air) in %	40	35	23	26

In view of the underlying narratives of particularly the three ambitious 1.5°C target decarbonization scenarios (therefore excluded the *Gradual Development* scenario), two interesting implications can be derived from the results here:

- In absolute terms, the *Techno-Friendly* scenario demonstrates the highest share of district heating with 20.09 TWh under the condition that district heating networks within the NUTS3 levels achieve the heat density benchmark of 10 GWh/km². The main driver for this is the significant penetration of (large-scale) heat pumps (air-sourced) that characterizes this scenario.
- Nevertheless, the implemented share of district heating in GENeSYS-MOD's district heating assumptions is the highest in the *Directed Transition* scenario and reaches 87 %. Also, this result is reflected in the fact that the share of large-scale heat pumps (air-sourced) achieves here its maximum with 40 %.

4.2.5 Key takeaways

The analyses have shown that the cost-effective heat supply at the European and national level in 2050 implies that district heating covers heat demand in 68 communities in Austria in 2050, which corresponds to 6% of the total number of communities. The results demonstrate that district heating continues to be picking cherries from beneficial areas (i.e., densely populated with high heat densities). However, the reduction of heat densities compared to today's values is mainly driven by a significant reduction of heat demands by building renovation measures and poses a challenge for district heating in the future. Nevertheless, the localization of district heating networks in the surrounding of urban areas indicates economic viability, too.

In view of comparing different scenarios in this work, the results indicate that the aggregate model GENeSYS-MOD is capable of handling planning approaches for decarbonization of energy systems. Particularly, the policy push in one of the scenarios (*Directed Transition*) is also reflected in the determined local heat densities of district heating. This can be seen in particular by the projected share of both district heating and large-scale heat pumps in GENeSYS-MOD's results.

This study can be anticipated as a starting point for discussing the role of district heating as an enabler for large-scale, highly efficient, and local integration of renewable heat sources such as geothermal, synthetic gas, hydrogen, and waste in sustainable energy systems with decreasing heat demands. Further research should follow on how obtained district heating networks and their heat densities (incl. the generation of large-scale heat pump (air) units) could be returned into more aggregate models, such as GENeSYS-MOD, in the sense of a feedback loop. That allows refining assumptions in the upper-level large-scale models, which in turn will increase the plausibility and realism of pathways at the European level.

4.3 Example: Deep decarbonization of a local urban neighbourhood (Vienna, Austria)

Note that essential parts of the content of the study presented in this Section 4.3 have already been published in the following journal, which acknowledges the support of the Open ENTRANCE project:

[26] S. Zwickl-Bernhard, H. Auer: "Demystifying natural gas distribution grid decommissioning: An open-source approach to local deep decarbonization of urban neighbourhoods", *Energy* 238 (2022), 121805, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.121805>

4.3.1 Objective of the study

The core objective of the following study is to investigate the decommissioning of the local distribution grid of natural gas (i.e., low-pressure range in the gas distribution grid up to 6 bar) in the heat supply of an urban neighborhood. This is also associated with a disconnection of the devices at the end-user's level, which are supplied directly with natural gas. In particular, the main research question is which alternative distribution grid capacities and sector coupling technologies are required to ensure an adequate, but sustainable development in the provision of local heat energy services (e.g., space heating and hot water). Two different local deep decarbonization pathways up to 2050, namely, electrification of all energy services and an expansion of the district heating network, play a key role in the analysis. Equally important in the study is the consideration of the increasingly important cooling demand service needs within the neighborhood, which have received little attention to date. In terms of empirical scenario settings like CO₂ price developments up to 2050 the *Gradual Development* decarbonization scenario in Open ENTRANCE is used, which refers to the 2.0°C climate target.

4.3.2 Method applied in the study

This study uses the two existing open-source models *rivus* [<https://github.com/tum-ens/rivus>] and *GUSTO* [<https://github.com/sebastianzwickl/GUSTO>]. Consequently, the approach provides a framework that includes a complete analysis toolbox using the different/unique model strengths. Thereby, *rivus* facilitates the modelling of the (local) energy system with a high spatial resolution. In contrast, *GUSTO*'s strength is modelling of local energy systems (i.e., small areas, such as neighbourhoods or communities) with a high temporal resolution (e.g., hourly). Exploiting the models' differences and strengths in a single analysis framework that arises by the coupling approach provides a comprehensive toolset to answer this work's research question. The two open-source models used are already applied in different scientific contributions (for details see [26]). For a comprehensive description of the two models as well as the specific functional extensions of the model *rivus* in terms of the implementation of the so-called "economies of scale" it is also referred to [26]. In this work, the economies of scale of a massive district heating and cooling network expansion are considered from the point of view of opportunity costs and penalties due to CO₂ emissions, rather

than from the specific investment costs of energy technologies and infrastructures as a result of large-scale market penetration due to technological learning rates.

4.3.3 Test bed description

In this study, a local natural gas distribution grid decommissioning and, consequently, natural gas phase-out in an urban neighbourhood in Vienna, Austria, is proposed. This area is located in parts of two Viennese districts (2nd and 3rd districts). In the analysis, special emphasis is placed on the spatial dispersion of the distribution grid capacity needs of a multiple-energy carrier energy system considering high shares of local renewable energy technology utilization. In particular, this neighbourhood is selected because it not only provides high diversity in (i) load profiles (electricity, heating, and cooling), (ii) building structures, and (iii) occupancy intensity but also describes a diverse representative urban area not only restricted to Austrian settlement patterns. Moreover, the characteristics of the test-bed include a residential area, public administration buildings, special consumers, a recreation area with selective energy service needs, a spatial separation by a river canal, cross-district administrative planning responsibilities, and more. Two more aspects related to the distribution grid analysis are important in this work. First, the local natural gas phase-out concerns the low-pressure grid in the range of 3–6 bar. Second, the electricity distribution grid capacities (in MW) considered neglect the detailed analysis of the different voltage levels ranging in Austria from 0.23 to 30 kV.

Scenario settings

In the following, three scenarios (including the current state of supply and two different local deep decarbonization pathways) are described narratively. The narratives are based on dedicated “what if/how” questions. The two local deep decarbonization pathways (Cases B and C) focus on distinct structural changes in the energy distribution grids and, subsequently, technology supply options feeding into these grids.

Case A - Baseline (current state of supply)

This scenario builds upon the existing distribution grid in the urban neighbourhood. It contributes to answer the question: what distribution grid capacities are available/required to supply the current local energy demand. Note, at present, there is no comprehensive cooling demand service available in the area. The distribution grid includes mainly electricity and gas infrastructure. Furthermore, the special consumers within the area are connected to and supplied by the district heating network only (see Figure 4–14, Figure 4–15 and Figure 4–16).

Figure 4-14 Local electricity distribution network in Case A - Baseline [26]

Figure 4-15 Local gas distribution network in Case A - Baseline [26]

Figure 4-16 Local district heating network in *Case A - Baseline* [26].

Case B - High electrification

In the high electrification scenario, the heat demand (previously mainly supplied by natural gas) is completely covered by electricity “fuelled” technologies (i.e., small-/large-scale heat pumps). Note that the special consumers within the area are still supplied by the district heating network. Furthermore, this scenario takes into account an expected increasing local cooling demand, which is delivered by electricity-based technologies (i.e., compression cooling machines). Thereby, the integration of high shares of local renewable energy generation plays a crucial role.

Case C - District heating/cooling network expansion

In this scenario the local natural gas distribution grid/demand is replaced by the district heating network supply. In addition, the increased cooling demand is covered by the district cooling network. Furthermore, the electricity demand remains constant in comparison with the current state of supply. Note that this distribution grid focused scenario places no emphasis on the energy generation technologies feeding into the heating/cooling grid. The technology portfolio in the district heating/cooling generation mix does not directly influence the distribution grid capacities determined in this analysis. Furthermore, this scenario considers a case study of the “non-discriminatory right” to be connected to the heating/cooling grid, regardless of the distance to the existing grid and heat/cold densities.

4.3.4 Results and discussion

Case A - Baseline

At present, high shares of the local energy demand are supplied by the electricity (Figure 4–14) and natural gas distribution grid (Figure 4–15). The mean electricity line capacity in the test-bed is 1.34 MW, and the maximum is 28.48 MW. The largest electricity line capacities serve as a grid connection capacity to the public grid and supply the three special consumers (*Stadium, University, and Fair*). The natural gas distribution network supplies almost the entire heat demand in the neighbourhood. In addition, the district heating network supplies heat demand of the three special consumer in the district (Figure 4–16). The maximum district heating line capacity is 7.61 MW. Note that *Case A* neglects cooling services because currently no district cooling network is implemented.

Figure 4–17 shows the distribution of line capacities for electricity, natural gas, and district heating using the so-called *violin plot*. For comparability, the width of the violin plots are relative to each other, where the one of electricity is set to 1. The wider the violin plot, the more lines (indicated with the grey points) are implemented in this capacity range. The horizontal bars indicate the mean line capacity value for each energy carrier distribution network. Figure 4–18 shows the total line length for the three energy carriers. Almost the same line lengths are required for electricity and natural gas, accounting for 96% of total local line lengths. Finally, Figure 4–19 shows a binary heat map for the networks of the three energy carriers electricity (top), natural gas (middle), and district heating (bottom). Each available distribution line is represented by a single element in the map. Note that the location of the elements is derived from the spatial setup in the Figure 4–14, Figure 4–15 and Figure 4–16.

Figure 4–17 Distribution of line capacities within the neighbourhood of electricity, natural gas, and district heating in Case A – Baseline [26].

Figure 4–18 Local distribution line length and its components in Case A – Baseline [26].

Figure 4–19 Binary heatmap of the local distribution network for electricity, natural gas, and district heating in Case A - Baseline [26].

Case B - Electrification

In this scenario, the urban neighbourhood pursues deep decarbonization by electrification of its energy supply. In addition, the natural gas phase-out in the heat supply, this scenario takes into account the cooling demand. The latter is mainly supplied by compression cooling machines. As a consequence, this further increases the local electricity demand. For example, the changes in the local energy system patterns are shown in Figure 4–20a. It shows the annual electricity duration curve for a characteristic multi-apartment building in the neighbourhood. Thereby, three different electrification levels are compared: (i) Baseline (*Case A - Baseline*), (ii) Heat (100%) considering the electrification of the heat demand only but neglecting the cooling demand, and (iii) a complete electrification (Heat and Cold (100%)). Figure 4–20b compares the total energy demand in *Case A - Baseline* and in *Case B - Electrification* for the same multi-apartment building. Note that this section's further results take into account the electrification of both heating and cooling demand (indicated by the blue duration line in Figure 4–20a). For the sake of clarity, a fully analogous result presentation similar to *Case A - Baseline* is omitted. Instead, Figure 4–21 presents the distribution line capacities (again by the *violin plot*) for the local electricity (left) and district heating (right) distribution grid.

Figure 4–20 Annual electricity duration curve and comparison of total energy demand for a multi-apartment building [26].

Figure 4–21 Distribution of line capacities within the neighborhood of electricity and district heating in Case A - Baseline. Comparing electricity line capacities in Case A and Case B [26].

Again, the mean line capacity values are marked by the horizontal bars. In addition, the three figures in the middle of Figure 4–21 highlight the differences of electricity line capacities between Case A – Baseline and Case B – Electrification (cut out of the line capacity frequency (top), max line capacity (middle), and mean line capacity (bottom)). Figure 4–22 shows the resulting local distribution line lengths for electricity and district heating. The latter are unchanged compared to Case A. The electricity distribution line lengths are split into two parts, namely, the existing share of Case A (light orange) and the extra share of Case B (rich orange).

Figure 4–22 Total line length and its components in Case B - Electrification [26].

The extended (binary) heat map in Figure 4–23 shows the use of local available distribution lines for electricity (top) and district heating (bottom). For district heating the same results occur as in Case A - Baseline as the existing network still supplies the special consumers' heat demand. For electricity

it mainly highlights the extra distribution lines demanded in *Case B – Electrification* (rich orange) compared with those in *Case A – Baseline* (light orange).

Figure 4-23 Extended heat map of local distribution network for electricity and district heating in *Case B – Electrification* [26].

Case C - District heating/cooling network expansion

Figure 4-24 shows the local distribution line capacities for district heating (left) and cooling (right). The district heating mean line capacity (top) and max line capacity compared with the *Case A – Baseline* is shown in the middle. It is evident that a significant increase for both is necessary to cover the heat demand. In addition, a massive expansion of the district cooling distribution grid is implemented, which is not existent in *Case A – Baseline*.

Figure 4-24 Distribution of line capacities of district heating and district cooling in *Case C*. Selected highlights comparing *Case B* and *Case C* [26].

The massive district heating and cooling network expansion is also reflected by the extended heatmap in Figure 4–25. The latter indicates a high level of available distribution line capacity utilization. Furthermore, it highlights available distribution line elements that are used for both district heating and cooling. The total distribution line length of the district heating network is 34.7 and 34.9 km of the district cooling network.

Figure 4–25 Local district heating and cooling network heatmap in Case C - Network [26].

Cost parity on building level for district heating/cooling expansion

The analysis below emphasizes the expansion of the district heating network on a large-scale in the entire supply area of the neighbourhood. This includes the associated “non-discriminatory right” of the end-users to be connected to the grid (*Case C - Network*). In particular, the analysis emphasizes the cost comparison between the current state of supply (*Case A - Baseline*) including its increasingly negative implications due to increasing CO_2 emission costs and the deep decarbonization pathway in *Case C - Network*. Figure 4–26 compares the average building costs within the neighbourhood in *Case A - Baseline* and *Case C - Network* for the heat demand supply taking into account a CO_2 price development according to the four different Open ENTRANCE scenarios.

In addition, two different scenarios of the district heating energy generation mix are illustrated. The first scenario includes no further decarbonization in the district heating fuelling energy mix and assumes that today's specific emissions remain constant until 2050. This assumption leads to average building cost parity between *Case A - Baseline* and *Case C - Network* in 2046 as indicated by the red diamond. Increasing decarbonization achievements of the district heating generation mix (i.e., stronger convex curvature of the solid black line *Case A - Baseline* as a result of halving district heating specific emissions from 2030) achieve earlier cost parity (green diamond in 2043). Moreover, the yellow marked area indicates the resulting total end-user cost-savings after the trade-off years. These cost-savings also increase with stronger convex curvature.

Figure 4-26 Cost parity on building level comparing Case A - Baseline and Case C - Network [26].

4.3.5 Key takeaways

Building upon a feasibility case study in an urban neighbourhood in Vienna, Austria, the analyses in this work not only have shown that deep decarbonization of a multiple-energy carrier system is possible, but this is also possible by decommissioning the local natural gas distribution grid. Against the background of the increasingly binding climate targets, it is very important to explore the full range of feasible options for sustainable local energy supply at the end-user's level off-limits, especially as the future potential and economic viability of green gas are uncertain at the end-user device level. Possible stranded assets must not play a decisive role, especially since the trade-off analyses in this work show that alternative network infrastructures and technologies of lower-emission or zero-emission energy service provision are even more economical in the medium to long term. It is also important to include the consideration of the increasingly important cooling service in the analysis.

Future work may focus, among others, on the following: (i) Detailed analyses of the energy generation technology portfolio feeding into the district heating/cooling grid, focusing in particular on co-firing with green gas, geothermal sources, solar-thermal, seasonal heat storage, and others. (ii) Consideration of the mobility sector and its local energy service needs (public versus private mobility), and finally (iii) higher granularity and spatial resolution of the building stock focusing on its efficiency, retrofitting measures, and implications of high shares of local (building-integrated) renewable generation in the context of energy community concepts.

4.4 Example: Decarbonization of heat supply in residential multi-apartment rental building (Vienna, Austria)

Note that essential parts of the content of the study presented in this Section 4.4 have already been published in the following journal, which acknowledges the support of the Open ENTRANCE project:

[27] S. Zwickl-Bernhard, H. Auer, A. Golab: “Equitable decarbonization of heat supply in residential multi-apartment rental buildings: Optimal subsidy allocation between the property owner and tenants”, *Energy and Buildings* 262 (2022), 112013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2022.112013>

4.4.1 Objective of the study

The core objective of this study is to set up a cost-optimal and socially balanced subsidization strategy for a multi-apartment building to trigger investments in a sustainable heat supply in line with the Open ENTRANCE scenario settings. A public authority (governance) incentivizes the replacement of the initial natural gas-based heating system toward a sustainable alternative along with building renovation measures (accompanied by reduced heat demand) by monetary support to the property owner and the tenants. Monetary support can be direct payments in the form of an investment grant for the property owner or a subsidy payment for the tenant. Besides, the property owner can also be indirectly financially supported by allowing a rent adjustment as the building is retrofitted. Social balance is defined at the building level from a monetary perspective using the net present value of the governance’s total payments for the building’s owner (or apartment’s owner) and the tenants.

In a more detailed consideration, the individual objectives of the different agents involved can be summarised as follows:

Governance: The governance’s main objective is to decarbonize the residential heating sector. Therefore, the policy is to trigger a heating system change to a sustainable alternative on the multi-apartment building level through financial support for both property owner and tenants. The avowed aim is to find a cost-minimal and socially balanced solution. The financial support for the property owner can be realized either or both by an investment grant (paid directly from the governance) and adjusted rent-charge-related revenues (paid from the tenants). The tenants, for their part, can be financially supported directly by the governance through heating costs subsidy payments.

Property owner: The property owner of the multi-apartment building provides the heating system for the tenants and is profit oriented. Thus, a heating system change toward a sustainable alternative is only realised in case of the economic viability of an investment. In this context, the property owner can achieve profitability of the alternative heating system by receiving an investment grant (to reduce the overnight investment costs) from the governance and a rent-charge-related revenue cash flow (from the tenants).

Tenant: The tenant rents a dwelling/unit within the multi-apartment building from the property owner and has rent-related and energy-related spending. The tenant cannot change the heating

system on its authority but depends on the property owner’s willingness to invest into a sustainable alternative. In connection with the existing heating system the tenant’s costs are increasing in consideration of CO₂ emissions and associated CO₂ prices. Nevertheless, the tenant aims to limit total costs in case of a heating system change at the level of the initial condition.

4.4.2 Method applied in the study

The method applied is the development of a linear optimization model. Thereby, the objective function is to minimize the governance’s net present value of monetary support over time. The property owner’s and tenants’ strategy to minimize individual total costs is considered by tailor-made constraints in the modelling framework. The generalized formulation of the model allows to investigate different building types and categorization (size and number of tenants, building efficiency, initial rent price, etc.). This can be helpful to analyse different building stocks.

Figure 4–27 shows a sketch illustrating the interrelations between the governance, the property owner, and the tenants. The governance can support the property owner financially by investment grants and by the permission of rent charge adjustments. At the same time, tenants are supported by a heating cost subsidy payment. The grey bar in the middle indicates that these financial benefits need to be socially balanced and overcome the differences in ownership within the multi-apartment building. The rent or rent charge adjustment is the direct financial exchange between the property owner and the tenant. For an analytical description of this set up it is referred to [27].

Figure 4–27 Model illustrating the interrelations between the governance, property owner, and tenants [27].

4.4.3 Test bed description

The numerical example examined is an old multi-apartment building with a single property owner and 30 units (tenants). The partially renovated building is located in an urban area (Vienna, Austria) and initially heated by individual gas heating systems at the unit's level. The decarbonization of the heat supply can be achieved by two different investment options, namely, a connection to the district heating network or an implementation of an air-sourced heat pump system on the building level. For a comprehensive overview of the empirical settings of the multi-apartment building including the agent's specific interest rates and further economic parameters it is referred to [27].

Scenario settings

Four different quantitative scenarios are studied with the tailor-made model presented above. Input settings of three of them are taken from Open ENTRANCE and describe a future European energy system development assuming to achieve the 1.5°C or 2.0°C climate target. These three scenarios are *Directed Transition* (DT), *Societal Commitment* (SC), and *Gradual Development* (GD). The first two scenarios consider the remaining CO₂ budget of the 1.5°C climate target. In addition to the three Open ENTRANCE scenarios, the so-called "*Low CO₂ price development*" (LD) scenario is examined. This scenario neglects any remaining European CO₂ budget and misses both the 1.5°C and 2.0°C climate target; thus, decarbonizing the electricity and heating sector develops only sluggishly. Therefore, neither the CO₂ price nor the specific emissions of electricity and district heating significantly changed with today's values. The CO₂ price in this scenario is between 60EUR/tCO₂ (in 2025) and 90EUR/tCO₂ (in 2040). No target year for achieving deep decarbonization of the European electricity and heating sector is set. Note that the four scenarios are used to set an empirical framework at the aggregate level for this work's analysis, which is carried out ultimately at the local level. Against this background, European decarbonization scenarios are projected to the building level, making them accessible in practical applications.

4.4.4 Results and discussion

This section elaborates on the results on the district heating option in the *Directed Transition* scenario first. Next, the focus is on the implementation of a heat pump system in the *Societal Commitment* scenario where the model indicates feasible solutions for a retrofitted building with a lower heat demand only (compared with the default settings). Then, a comparison of the results of the district heating and heat pump-based heat supply in the different scenarios quantified in this work is conducted. Finally, the results in case of varying CO₂ pricing cost allocation between the property owner and the tenants are presented.

District heating in the *Directed Transition* scenario

This section presents the results of the district heating implementation in the *Directed Transition* scenario in detail. Figure 4–28 shows the net present value of cash flows in general, and revenues in particular, of the property owner and a single tenant within the time horizon of 2025–2040. The top

left presents the different items of the property owner consisting of the overnight investment costs, investment grant, and rent-related revenues. Note that the latter represent the additional rent-related revenues due to the newly installed sustainable heating system. The bottom left shows the development of the property owner's net present value of their cash flow over time. Thereby, it is shown that the investment pays off for the property owner by zero in 2040. The righthand side in Figure 4–28 illustrates the corresponding tenant's cash flow items (top) and total net present value (bottom) until 2040.

The tenant receives subsidy payments from the governance between 2025 and 2030. Thus, the tenant's net present value in 2040 matches with the value as in the reference case. The reference case considers constant remaining rent and heat-related costs for the tenant based on the initial rent, gas-based heat system parameters, and CO₂ prices as of 2025. In the years 2025-2029, the subsidy payments exceed the heating costs of the tenant. Note that the tenant already pays a higher rent charge to the property owner within the same period (see the yellow bars in Figure 4–28 top left). Most importantly, the tenant's reference net present value ("Ref. (Gas/2025)"; grey dashed line in the Figure 4–28 bottom right) shows a crucial aspect of the results and assumptions of the analysis which requires an explanation. Since "Ref. (Gas/2025)" is used as the initial tenant's spendings, the results also take into account the total opportunity costs (i.e., those costs that would be incurred by sticking to the initial gas-based heating system for the tenant due to a rising CO₂ price). Note that the Open ENTRANCE decarbonization scenarios used in this work do consider both a significant increase of the CO₂ price and a decrease of the specific emissions of the district heating and electricity fuelling mix. The quantitative results indicate that the heating system change in this scenario is achieved with manageable total governance subsidies. However, a detailed discussion of the allocation of CO₂ price-related opportunity costs is conducted in final result section.

Figure 4–28 Development of the property owner's and tenant's economic viability of the district heating option in the *Directed Transition* scenario [27].

Heat pump and building stock quality in the *Societal Commitment* scenario

Interestingly, the model indicates for the heat pump implementation in the *Societal Commitment* scenario an infeasible solution. The reason for that is, among others (investment costs of the air-sourced heat pump and the electricity price), the high heating demand used in the default input settings. Therefore, in the following the focus is put on the impact of different building renovation levels, the associated heating demand decrease, and finally the impact on the feasibility of the model.

Figure 4–29 shows the results of the heat pump implementation in the *Societal Commitment* scenario for four different building qualities (and thus heat demand levels) in detail. Since the initial setting of the default building in terms of total and peak heat demand leads to the infeasibility of the model, the following three additional renovation levels are studied: 10%, 20%, and 30% reduction of both the total and peak heat demands. In Figure 4–29 (top left), the corresponding settings of the specific heat load (describing building quality) are indicated. In case of a 10% reduction of the heat demand, the property owner receives a significant investment grant equivalent to 29% of the property owner's total overnight investment costs of the building retrofitting measures (top right). The associated tenant's subsidy payment takes place between 2025 and 2030 with a maximum of 2 040EUR/year (bottom left). The rent charge adjustment and related revenues remain almost constant during the period (bottom right). In case of a 20% reduction of the heat demand, the property owner receives only a small investment grant related to the total overnight investment costs (2%). The tenant's

subsidy payment takes place between 2025 and 2032 with a maximum of 2 556EUR/year. The property owner's rent-related revenues increase until 2031 and then remain constant. In case of a 30% reduction of the heat demand, the property owner receives as before a small investment grant (3%). Instead, the property owner makes significant rent-related revenues (the highest among the three renovation levels). The tenant gets subsidy payments in most years, excluding 2026 and 2028 to 2030 (mainly as a result of the matching of the CO₂ price and the specific CO₂ emissions of the fuelling energy mix). The maximum is 2 796EUR/year in 2040. The lower heat energy-related costs as a result of the building renovation leads to higher rent charge payments. Hence, smaller investment grants supporting the property owner are sufficient.

Figure 4-29 Comparison of the heat pump option in the Societal Commitment scenario for different renovation levels [27].

Governance's total subsidies in the different scenarios

In the following, a comparison of the governance's total subsidies for district heating (DH) or heat pump (HP) implementation in the different scenarios is conducted (see also Figure 4-30):

- The total subsidies across the three district heating cases are relatively stable and are within 11.2%.
- The heat pump implementation in the two decarbonization scenarios *Societal Commitment* and *Gradual Development* is infeasible for the default setting of the building quality.
- Only the low CO₂ price development scenario provides a solution for the heat pump but with a significantly higher subsidy +82.6% compared with the lowest subsidy scenario.

- The public financial deficit (governance’s total financial support minus CO₂ tax revenues) is the lowest (144.8 thousand EUR) in the *Directed Transition* scenario.

Finally, it is important to note that the property owner’s rent-related revenues (orange bar) are an “implicit” subsidy. Hence, the governance’s total financial support is equal to the sum of the tenants’ heating costs subsidy (purple bar) and the property owner’s investment grant (blue bar).

Figure 4–30 Comparison of governance’s total financial support for the property owner and the tenants for the district heating (DH) and heat pump (HP) implementations [27].

Allocation of CO₂ pricing related costs between the governance, property owner, and tenant

This section examines the impact of the costs of inaction (i.e., sticking to the initial gas-based heating system) on the governance’s total financial support. In detail, this means that the CO₂ costs (i.e., opportunity costs) to be expected due to increasing CO₂ prices have to be allocated to the different parties/agents (or a single one): governance, property owner, and tenant. Table 4–6 shows the objective value (absolute value and relative change in % from GD (DH)) for different allocations of opportunity costs. Exemplarily, “Equally” (first row) takes into account that the CO₂ costs are shared equally among the governance, property owner, and tenants. Each of them bears one third of the costs. Note that the scenario setups (i.e., GD (DH)) considered so far that the total costs of inaction are covered by the governance.

Table 4–6 Comparison of objective value for varying allocations of CO₂-related opportunity costs [27].

Brief summary	Rel. allocation of opportunity costs			Objective value	
	Governance	Property owner	Tenant	Absolute in EUR	Rel. change in % from GD (DH)
Equally	$\frac{1}{3}$	$\frac{1}{3}$	$\frac{1}{3}$	146.6	-25%
Property owner & tenant	0	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	129.0	-34%
Property owner	0	1	0	99.7	-49%
Governance & tenant	$\frac{1}{2}$	0	$\frac{1}{2}$	183.8	-6%
GD (DH) (Governance)	1	0	0	195.5	-

The highest total subsidy reduction is obtained when the property owner has to cover the costs of inaction (-49% compared with the reference value). The second highest reduction is achieved when the opportunity costs are shared equally within the building among the property owner and tenants (-34%). Equally allocated opportunity costs reduce the total subsidy by 25%. It is evident that an even allocation between the governance and the tenants hardly leads to a reduction of the objective value. The main reason for this is the financial support of the property owner, which is necessary to create an investment incentive, and the fact that the financial support between the property owner and tenants necessarily has the same net present value.

Building upon, Figure 4–31 shows the objective value for the varying property owner’s interest rates. The varying property owner’s interest rates have two important impacts. First, a decreasing interest rate reduces the objective value as revenues are discounted less (see Figure 4–31 for a fixed property owner’s share in costs of inaction, e.g., 0.2). Second, as the interest rate decreases, a feasibility limit becomes apparent. This means that the feasible maximum of the property owner’s share in costs of inaction depends on the property owner’s interest rate. Two interesting energy policy implications can be derived from the results here:

- In case the property owner is very much profit-oriented (e.g., interest rate of 10%) and the governance’s total subsidy payments are to be kept as low as possible, complete allocation of the CO₂-related opportunity costs to the property owner results in a cost-optimal strategy.
- In contrast, in case the property owner rather serves a public-benefit purpose (e.g., interest rate of 3%), the CO₂-related opportunity costs allocation among governance, property owner, and tenants is an adequate strategy.

Figure 4–31 Comparison of the objective value for varying property owner’s interest rates and share in costs of inaction [27].

4.4.5 Key takeaways

In this study it is found that a fair and equitable switch to a sustainable heat system is possible but with massive public subsidy payments. In particular, the property’s owner investment grant and additional rent-related revenues derived from the building renovation measures are crucial to trigger the profitability of the investment. At the same time, subsidy payments to the tenants are required at the beginning of the investment period to limit the energy- and rent-related spendings. Furthermore, the results impressively show that the heat pump alternative is not competitive in supplying heat service needs in partly renovated old buildings. Either the subsidy payments are significantly higher than in the district heating case, or the equity constraints of the model can’t be satisfied. Deep building renovation and associated reduction of heat demand enable feasible solutions but with high total costs. In this case, passive retrofitting measures need to be incentivized, too.

Furthermore, the results demonstrate that allocating the costs of inaction between the governance, the property owner, and the tenants is an important lever and can reduce the required subsidy payments. First and foremost, the biggest drop of the total subsidies (to nearly half) takes place when the costs of inaction are completely borne by the property owner. Also, a decrease in the property owner’s interest rate reduces the total costs but limits the maximum share of the costs of inaction allocated to the property owner and implies a lower bound of the cost-minimized solution.

Future work may investigate a stronger coupling of active and passive building renovation measures as a necessary precondition for subsidy payments. This could bring further insights to decarbonization and public financial strategies with an eye on the heat demand and sustainable heat source alternatives in the multi-apartment residential building sector (i.e., climate neutrality in 2050). In this context, further in-depth analyses regarding the public financial deficit (i.e., the interaction between governance's subsidy payments and CO₂ tax revenues) should be conducted for different sustainable technology alternatives and retrofitting levels. Besides, the tenant's diversification within the building could be improved (e.g., different willingness to pay to contribute to CO₂ mitigation). More generally, this study could be extended by introducing further technology options, such as solar PV and heat and electricity storage systems.

5 Synthesis of results and concluding remarks

Deliverable D3.2 has demonstrated that breaking down aggregate modeling results to ever smaller spatial system boundaries is possible and very important in practice for energy policy decision making. Starting from the pan-European level, Open ENTRANCE results have been presented in a consistent and coherent manner on European country-level, further down to representative region and local-level and finally even beyond on building/end-user level.

Chapter 2 presents at the beginning the refinements made to GENeSYS-MOD and the Open ENTRANCE dataset since the last deliverable that was published in 2020. The improvements include both major changes to the code and mathematical formulation of GENeSYS-MOD, as well as a complete overhaul of the used European dataset, adding new data, removing potential error sources, updating various assumptions, etc. With both of these areas covered, the new pan-European storylines that are presented within this Deliverable D3.2 are vastly improved compared to their previous iteration. The new pathway results allow for an in-depth analysis of both the European energy system at an aggregate level, as well as country-level analyses, offering insights into developments within the modeled regions. The pathway results show that on a European level, rapid change is required to fulfill the ambitious climate goals that are stated within the storylines. For this, a massive expansion of (renewable) electricity generation, coupled with heavy investments into storages, transmission capacities, and hydrogen generation infrastructure are necessary. This rapid transformation of the energy system comes with a significant increase in electrification, encompassing all European countries.

Chapter 3 gives some insights about the developments in the different scenarios on a country-level. In this regard, this chapter showed an overview of selected results for the modeled countries, followed by an in-depth presentation of selected EU Member States (i.e., Germany, France, and Spain). In general, electricity generation rises significantly across all pathways, mostly due to the high degree of sector-coupling and direct and indirect electrification. The overall results show that a mix of different variable renewable energy sources is used for providing electricity for most European countries. In this regard, a heavy reliance on solar PV in southern parts of Europe and on wind in the northern parts can be observed. Hydrogen and synthetic methane play only minor roles in the power sector. In this chapter, the diametrical development of energy dependence in the modeled region is highlighted. Depending on the potentials of renewable energy sources and the domestic energy demands, some countries become substantial net-exporters of energy. In contrast, others see an increase in net electricity or hydrogen imports. In this regard, especially Spain and Turkey become major energy providers for the rest of the European area. Especially the disparity between hydrogen consumers and producers is further highlighted in this chapter. Also, the country-specific results

show in detail the importance for short- as well as long-term storages for the stability of the power system. Subsequently, the necessity of cross-border electricity interconnections for providing flexibility becomes clear. Overall, this shows that for a cost-optimal energy transition, cross-border transport of hydrogen and electricity will play a key role and, thus, need to be further incentivized. Lastly, the dispatch results of the specific countries show that conventional generators (if any exist in 2050), as well as biomass power plants, only have minor up-times throughout the years and, therefore, policies and regulations need to be adapted to allow them to be profitable in a renewable dominated energy system.

Chapter 4 presents region-level results for the cases of Norway and Turkey. To allow for more detailed analysis of these countries, they have been disaggregated in 5 and 12 regions respectively. The disaggregation method used for the two cases has been similar, with relying on industry locations for the disaggregation of industrial heat demands, population for the residential heating, electricity and transport demand and land area for resource potential, whenever there is no data available for the disaggregated level. Scenario results show that Norway will increase its electricity production considerably, mainly from hydropower and new offshore wind installations. Electricity demand increases come from transport sector and for hydrogen production, used both as a flexibility measure (storage) and an energy carrier for industry and exports. The disaggregated model gives insights into the differences on a bidding zone level, showing that the electricity production mix will be dominated by hydropower for all regions except NO3, which will see significant offshore wind resources exploited. Given Norway's large geographical reach, average wind and solar profiles will yield results that can be significantly improved by modelling on a more disaggregated level and with regionally appropriate profiles. On the other hand, spatial disaggregation of Turkish energy system into NUTS level 1 regions with better time series (capacity factor) estimation for solar PV and wind in each region allows a) more investments in solar PV technologies by 2050; b) more hydrogen production and use by 2050 c) penetration of electricity and hydrogen storage technologies as early as 2025 when compared to the aggregated model results. For future research, a more detailed spatial (e.g., NUTS level 3 regions with 81 provinces) and temporal (e.g., 72 hours step) disaggregation study will be analysed.

Last but not least, downscaling algorithms are presented to demonstrate the usefulness of overarching Open ENTRANCE scenario results also for “last-mile” analyses and decision making on municipal, neighborhood and building level where individual end-users are directly affected. In future work the insights gained on the finest granularity levels could also be returned into more aggregate models again, such as GENE SYS-MOD, in the sense of a feedback loop. That allows refining assumptions in the upper-level large-scale models, which in turn will increase the plausibility and realism of pathways at the European level.

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Appendix

Input data settings

Large-scale energy system models such as GENeSYS-MOD require a multitude of different input datapoints to run. This means that input data collection is a major part of the work when generating results, such as for this Deliverable. Many times, these input data sources do not cover every single country within the scope or do not cover the same level of detail. This means that in order to cover all required information for every region and year included in the model calculations, oftentimes, many different sources need to be considered at once, especially when only publicly available, open sources, are to be considered. This creates large, convoluted datasets with a wide range of dependencies. While it is difficult to provide sources for every single datapoint, the following table lists the most relevant data sources that have been used for generating the European dataset used in this study. Also, the dataset, as well as the accompanying source code will be uploaded to the open platform, so that everyone is free to check the data for themselves, run the model(s), and validate the results.

Sector		Source	Comment
Transport	Passenger	EU transport in figures	only road, train, air are considered. no short-distance public transport
	Freight	EU transport in figures	only road, train, ship are considered.
Electricity	2018 Generation numbers	IEA Country Data	
	residual capacities	EUROSTAT	
	residual capacities (wind)	WindEurope	
Resources	Biomass potentials	EC Biomass futures atlas	
Industry	Low-temperature industrial heat	Naegler et al. (2015)	currently double accounting for low-temperature usage in commercial buildings -> will be moved to buildings
	Medium-temperature industrial heat	Fraunhofer (2012)	Fraunhofer source for 2012, interpolated to 2018 using EUROSTAT data changes
	High-temperature industrial heat	Fraunhofer (2012)	Fraunhofer source for 2012, interpolated to 2018 using EUROSTAT data changes
Buildings		Fraunhofer ISI et al. (2016)	
Technologies	Efficiencies (electricity & heat)		2018 taken from source, afterwards development dependent on pathway assumptions
	Efficiencies (transport)	Pagenkopf et al. (2019)	
	CO ₂ content of fuels	IPCC (2006)	CO ₂ emission factors for combustion, default values
Timeseries data	Electricity (load)	DynElmod input data	
	Renewable timeseries (PV, Wind)	renewables.ninja	offshore wind grouping manual by distance to shore; PV and onshore wind based on yearly full-load hours, divided into optimal, average, inferior placements
	Transport	Gruschwitz and Follmer (2013)	one hourly profile for an average day (24 consecutive hours) is taken and repeated for every day
	Industry	Own calculation	own assumptions on load curves based on industry type, described in the GENeSYS-MOD 2.0 data documentation
	Heatpumps	The Weather Company	capacity factor calculated dependent on outside temperature, COP _{HP} , Carnot = TH/(TH-TL) (Air source uses air outside temperature and ground source uses ground temperature; T _H is set to room temperature)
	Building Heat	The Weather Company	dependent on outside temperature -> target temperature of 18°C at night and 21°C during the day, difference creates profile for space heating demand; warm water is added as a fixed term
CO ₂ Price			assumptions, generated by model results, aiming at 100% decarbonization in 2040 (1.5 degree pathways) or 100% decarbonization by 2050 (2 degree pathway); CO ₂ price resembles the price needed to achieve this degree of decarbonization in said year

Table A 1: Data sources used for the model calculations

Additional Pan-European scenario results

Figure A 1 Industry

Figure A 2 Buildings

Figure A 3 Passenger Transport

Figure A 4 Freight Transport

Figure A 5 Capacities

Figure A 6 Hydrogen generation and use, including storages and liquefaction

Country-specific scenario results

Figure A 7

Figure A 8

Figure A 9

Figure A 10

Figure A 11

Figure A 12

Figure A 13

Figure A 14

Figure A 15

Figure A 16

Figure A 17

Figure A 18

Figure A 19

Figure A 20

Figure A 21

Figure A 22

Figure A 23

Figure A 24

Figure A 25

Figure A 26

Figure A 27

Figure A 28

Figure A 29

Figure A 30

Figure A 31

Figure A 32

Figure A 33

Figure A 34

Figure A 35

Figure A 36

Region-specific scenario results

TURKEY

Additional comments: Computational issues with the GENeSYS-MOD Turkey model

We have employed the source code for GENeSYS-MOD v3.0 and used GAMS IDE version 34.3.0 with Gurobi version 9.1.1 and CONOPT3 version 3.17L on a server (Intel Xeon CPU E5-2620 v2 @ 2.10GHz (2 processors) with 12 physical cores, 24 logical processors using up to 22 threads) with 160 GB RAM.

We have encountered numeric problems while running our disaggregated models. Most common issues are summarized below:

1. Barrier method: In scenario runs, the barrier method (“method 2” in GAMS/GUROBI options) is used and it was always sub-optimal, which requires many crossover iterations in solving the large-scale GENeSYS-MOD model (a linear program, LP, with ~11 million rows, ~14 million columns and ~36 million nonzeros)
2. Numeric errors in crossover and simplex algorithm: In some scenarios (specifically Gradual Development), the algorithm stalled at the crossover stage and diverged to non-optimal solutions with a huge primal-dual gap. In some cases, the GUROBI solver stops with “Numeric error” message.
3. In many cases, time limit of 400,000 seconds is reached.

In order to resolve these issues, we have employed several strategies:

- 1 Hotstart for LP: This is a common strategy where there are time limitations and one would like to start from a known solution, mostly sub-optimal. We modified the switches available in GENeSYS-MOD source code (specifically, “invlimit” switch) to find sub-optimal solutions. We then resolved the problem with simplex or dual simplex algorithm (using “method 5” in GAMS/GUROBI options) by hotstarting from this sub-optimal solution. In many cases, this strategy allowed us to obtain the results for many scenarios in a reasonable time (i.e., less than 400,000 seconds).
- 2 GUROBI options “Numericfocus” and “CrossoverBasis”: GAMS/GUROBI options “Numericfocus 2” and “CrossoverBasis 1” options were useful in solving divergent or numerically ill LPs.

Figure A 37 Power Dispatch in Turkey

Figure A 38 Power Capacity in Turkey

Figure A 39 Passenger transport in Turkey

Figure A 40 Freight transport in Turkey

Figure A 41 Building heat in Turkey

Industrial Heat

Figure A 42 Industrial heat in Turkey

Emissions

Figure A 43 Emissions in Turkey

